

Integrated interdisciplinary analysis report

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Executive Summary

This document describes the outcome of the data analysis for the use cases in the DIAMOND project as part of Work Package 4 and the development of a socio demographic model for inclusiveness self-evaluation on various application based on the results of the WP. Specifically, it will provide a representation of the knowledge acquired in this WP and how it should feed the Diamond model, which will represent the first produced output, and the lessons learnt from the data analysis. This task also summarized the knowledge acquired from workshops organized one in month 25 and one in month 28, involving experts from the Advisory Board to get their opinions and feedback on the interdisciplinary analysis findings. All partners who have carried out the studies participate in the integration of their results. The output produced by this WP was provided to WP5 for the development of the Toolbox.

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Terminology and Acronyms

ADAS	<i>Advanced Driving Assistance System</i>
ADS	<i>Automated Driving System</i>
AITEC	<i>Aitec Asesores Internacionales srl</i>
AHP	<i>Analytic Hierarchy Process</i>
API	<i>Application Programming Interface</i>
AV	<i>Automated Vehicles</i>
BN	<i>Bayesian Network</i>
CAV	<i>Connected autonomous vehicle</i>
CBI-R	<i>Career Barriers Inventory-Revised</i>
CCTV	<i>Closed-circuit Television</i>
CF	<i>Concept of Fairness</i>
CFCs	<i>Cluster of Fairness Characteristics</i>
CSR	<i>Corporate Social Responsibility</i>
DAD	<i>Dynamic Argumentative Delphi</i>
DDT	<i>Dynamic Driving Tasks</i>
ENU	<i><u>Edinburgh Napier University</u></i>
EU	<i>European Union</i>
EURECAT	<i>Eurecat - Centro Tecnológico de Cataluña</i>
FCs	<i>Fairness Characteristics</i>
FGC	<i>Ferrocarrils de la Generalitat de Catalunya</i>
FTTE	<i>University of Belgrade</i>
G&V	<i>Genre et Ville</i>
GHG	<i>Greenhouse Gas</i>
GIS	<i>Geographic Information System</i>
GPS	<i>Global Positioning System</i>
HAV	<i>Highly Automated Vehicles</i>
HMI	<i>Human Machine Interface</i>
HR	<i>Human Resources</i>
IBV	<i>Instituto de Biomecánica</i>
ID	<i>Inclusion Diamond</i>
IPs	<i>Influencing Parameters</i>

<i>M</i>	<i>Month</i>
<i>OAPs</i>	<i>Old Age Pensioners</i>
<i>OSM</i>	<i>Open Street Map</i>
<i>PI</i>	<i>Polyhedral Individual</i>
<i>PPE</i>	<i>Personal Protective Equipment</i>
<i>RINA</i>	<i>Rina Services spa</i>
<i>SD</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>
<i>STIR</i>	<i>University of Stirling</i>
<i>SYS</i>	<i>Systematica srl</i>
<i>TU Dublin</i>	<i>Technological University Dublin</i>
<i>UESI</i>	<i>Users and Employees' Satisfaction Index questionnaires</i>
<i>UC1</i>	<i>Use Case I</i>
<i>UC2</i>	<i>Use Case II</i>
<i>UC3</i>	<i>Use Case III</i>
<i>UC4</i>	<i>Use Case IV</i>
<i>VELIB</i>	<i>Syndicat Mixte Autolib et Velib Métropole</i>
<i>WAVE</i>	<i>Wave Women and Vehicles in Europe</i>
<i>WP</i>	<i>Work Package</i>
<i>ZTM</i>	<i>Miasto Stoleczne Warszawa</i>

I Introduction

This document describes the outcome of the data analysis for the use cases in the DIAMOND project as part of Work Package 4. Therefore, it provides an overview of the various data set collected and analysed the results of the analysis and how they were used to formulate an integrated interdisciplinary approach for the representing the knowledge acquired in this WP into a So-called Fairness Maturity model that users can apply for self-evaluation and benchmarking purposes. The model has been applied and declined to the four uses cases considered in the project. This represent one of the main produced output, and the lessons learnt from the data analysis that was passed on to WP 5 for the development of the on-line toolbox. This task also summarized the knowledge acquired from workshops organized one in month 25 and one in month 28, involving experts from the Advisory Board to get their opinions and feedback on the interdisciplinary analysis findings. All partners who have carried out the studies participate in the integration of their results

2 The DIAMOND approach for interdisciplinary analysis: datasets and results summary

In this deliverable we aim to provide an overview of the qualitative and quantitative data collected and the analysis we performed with it in Diamond in relation to the four use cases we had direct access to. The use cases were aimed at finding key drivers for supporting the inclusion of women in transport systems as both users and employees:

- Use Case I: Public Transport Infrastructures (Railways);
- Use Case II: (Emotion in) Autonomous Passenger Car;
- Use Case III: Vehicle (Bike) Sharing Fleet Management;
- Use Case IV: Employment of Women in Rail Industry and Freight/CSR Protocols

In the following chapters we will provide a summary review of the data and results obtained, the workshops organised to revise those results and the contribution in terms of a Fairness Maturity Model for Diamond to be used by transport organisations to evaluate and identify area of improvements.

2.1 Overview of the Data and Analysis Gathered for Each Use Case

Data collection campaigns have been based on the methodological approach of the DIAMOND project. This relies on the Fairness Characteristics (FCs) identified through a Thematic Analysis of the relevant literature and on a series of interdisciplinary tools and methods (as listed below). The heterogeneous and disaggregated datasets gathered through the executed data collection campaigns are classified in three main categories:

The gathered datasets are divided into three main categories:

- **Thematic analysis:**
 - Literature review (Use Case I, II, III and IV);

- Focus groups (Use Case I, II, III and IV);
 - Semi-structured Interviews (Use Case I, II, and IV).
- **Service and Employers' Provision Data:**
 - Structured data regarding the operation of transport services (Use Cases I and III) and job holders of the sector (Use Case IV);
 - Observations regarding relevant features of transportation settings (Use Cases I and III) and emotional responses to autonomous vehicles (Use Case II);
 - Users and Employees' Satisfaction Index questionnaires regarding the opinion of the end-users of the services (Use Cases I, II and III) and job conditions and employability (Use Case IV);
 - Social media data from Twitter regarding geospatial/time-based information and the opinion of the end-users of the services (Use Cases I, II and III).
 - **Users and Employees' Perception Data:**
 - DAD-Dynamic Argumentative Delphi survey questionnaires regarding the Fairness Characteristics (Use Cases I, II, III and IV).
 - Users and Employees' Satisfaction Index questionnaires regarding the opinion of the end-users of the services (Use Cases I, II and III) and job conditions and employability (Use Case IV);
 - Social media data from Twitter regarding geospatial/time-based information and the opinion of the end-users of the services (Use Cases I, II and III).

The information gathered from the other deliverables in Work package 4 helped to support this deliverable. 'Deliverable 4.1 Data sets description' describes the data collection activities executed within the 'Work Package 3 – Data collection' of the DIAMOND project (from M9-July 2019 to M25-November 2020). It includes information regarding the identification of data set sources, data collection tools, data collection timeline and the partners of the Consortium responsible for each data collection activity.

'Deliverable 4.2 Socio-Economic, Demographic and Psychological Analysis' built on the literature reviewed in Work Packages 2 and the data collected in Work Package 3 and is closely linked to not only this deliverable but also D4.3. It sought to take stock of the existing literature already analysed in WP 3 and developed further defined concepts which will support the thematic analysis in Task 4.1 and answered important research questions, e.g. What are the key factors affecting women's travel choices? D4.2 presented a definition of fairness as operationalised in the DIAMOND project and the results of a scoping review for each project Use Case.

'Deliverable 4.3 Computational analysis report' offers an explanation of the data analysis, each data analysis and its results are explained in depth in the different sections of the deliverable. The information from the Focus Groups and semi-structured interviews was useful to determine important qualitative factors and fairness measures (FM) to be included in the Maturity Model table. User generated content from social media was studied as a complementary data source, to obtain insights on the main concerns of men and women with respect to the different use cases from a larger base of users than the surveys' respondents. Structured data and observations were

analysed to characterize railways stations (Use Case I) and docking stations (Use Case III) along different dimensions, and to develop indexes embedding mobility, socio-demographic and territorial aspects. For Use Case II, experimental analysis with a simulator was performed to assess the emotional reaction of different demographic groups of people to autonomous vehicles' driving experience. It presented the findings of our results by methodology and summarised the key findings for each Use Case to provide an overview for discussion and to better inform the development of the integrated interdisciplinary analysis that was used to deliver a Fairness Maturity Model (D4.4).

The information and results from these earlier deliverables can be seen below in the current lessons learnt from each Use Case. These will help to further propose Fairness measures to achieve a more inclusive transport system for women users and employees.

2.1.1 Data set and Current lessons learnt from Use case I

The objective of the Use Case I 'Public Transport Infrastructures (Railways)' is to investigate women's needs as users of metro and urban railway infrastructures and is aimed at supporting the development of gender-equitable transport planning and design policies. The final goal of the Use Case I is to increase the percentage of women using metro and commuter railway public transports.

The methodology for data collection¹ for the Use Case I consisted of the following:

- Service and Employers' Provision Data:
 - Structured data regarding the transport settings and the operation of the service;
 - Observations regarding universal design indicators of the infrastructures;
 - UESI questionnaires regarding the opinion of the end-users;
 - Social media data regarding the opinion of the end-users;
 - Online semi structured interviews and Focus groups
- Users and Employees' Perception Data:
 - DAD survey questionnaires regarding the opinion of the end-users.

Service and Employers' Provision Data (only Service Provision Data in this case) were collected focusing on the metro and commuter urban railway stations managed by FGC-Ferrocarrils de la Generalitat de Catalunya (Province of Barcelona, Spain) and by ZTM-Miasto Stoleczne Warszawa (Warsaw Metropolitan Area, Poland) and Irish rail. Users and Employees' Perception Data (only Users Perception Data in this case) were collected focusing on the opinion of the end-users across several European Countries.

The data gathered for this use case is represented in the following table.

¹ See 'Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection'.

Table 1: overview of data sources collected and analysed for Use case I

Data Typology	Sources	Time Period	Data Designer	Set Collector
Structured Data	Open data and proprietary data.	M9-M17 (Completed)	SYS.	FGC, SYS, ZTM.
Observations	CFCs (Level 1), FCs (Level 2), Influencing Parameters (Level 3).	M15 (Completed)	SYS, ZTM.	FGC, ZTM.
UESI questionnaires and follow up protocol (which involved Focus groups and interviews)	CFCs (Level 1), FCs (Level 2), Influencing Parameters (Level 3).	M16-M24 (Completed)	G&V, STIR, Dublin.	SYS, TU FGC, ZTM.
Social Media Data	Twitter (disaggregated) data.	M14-M24 (Completed)	EUT, SYS.	EUT.
DAD survey questionnaires	CFCs (Level 1), FCs (Level 2).	M15-M24 (Completed)	AITEC.	AITEC, EUT, FTTE, G&V, IBV, TU Dublin, SYS, WAVE, ZTM.

2.1.1.1 Structured Data

The aim of the structured data collection (from M9-July 2019 to M17-March 2020) was to select and characterize a sample of 10 suitable stations managed by the Spanish organization (FGC) (82 stations in total) and the Polish organisation (ZTM) (96 stations in total). Structured Open Data were retrieved, sorted and filtered from open data repositories, national geoportals and census databases in order to identify specific stations to be used.

Preliminary structured open data analysis was based on Geographic Information Systems (GIS). A series of thematic maps² related to the localization and density distribution of data sets were

² See 'Deliverable 3.3 Report on data collection campaigns.

designed to assess the level of accessibility of the railway network managed by the Spanish and Polish organisations, focusing on territorial data, socio-demographic data, mobility data and railway network data.

Raw data related to the urban scale were extracted on surrounding areas around each station within a catchment area of 400 meter, commonly known as comfortable walkable distance. Data were post-processed through:

1. Density-based calculation on buffer areas;
2. Normalization of values (z values in a range between 0 and 1);
3. Weighted formulas of normalized values to prioritize certain indicators.

The proposed approach allowed the calculation of territorial data index (TDI), sociodemographic data index (SDDI) and mobility data index (MDI). Quintile frequency distribution of results allowed the identification of positively relevant stations and negatively relevant stations. This approach allowed for the identification of a short list of stations, characterized by positively and negatively relevant characteristics related to the objectives of the Use Case I, levels of accessibility for women.

Further characterization was done using Structured Proprietary Data that focused on travel demand data, reliability of the service, accessibility of the service, security of the transport infrastructures.

The proposed methodology helped to identify a group of suitable urban railway stations belonging at least two highest or lowest quintiles among the Territorial Data Index, Sociodemographic Data Index and Mobility Data Index. The list was further shortened through the analysis of several open data related to each railway infrastructure: (i) metro and urban railway lines; (ii) transport service tariff zone; (iii) underground or above-ground infrastructure.

Within the objectives of DIAMOND, the results of the proposed analysis allowed to identify an appropriate sample of urban railway infrastructures to be further investigated through on-site observations focused on universal design indicators and social media data collection and survey questionnaires focused on women passengers' needs and expectations.

2.1.1.2 [Observations](#)

After the structured open data was carried out onsite non-participatory observations could be made. These observations were aimed at further characterizing the metro and commuter urban railway stations. Observations were based on an ad hoc designed checklist defined by SYS with the support of the Spanish and Polish organisations for the evaluation of relevant infrastructure design and surrounding context characteristics related to women's needs in public transport infrastructure. The checklist was comprised of four main parts: (i) area surrounding the station; (ii) concourse level of the station; (iii) platform level of the station; (iv) carriage. Onsite observations took the form of researchers visually observing the public moving around inside the stations and using facilities and recording their finding on paper. Results were organized in a tabular structure based on a collaborative Excel worksheet. In addition, some still photographs of the metro and urban railway stations were collected out for full details of observation analysis please see D4.3

2.1.1.3 Users and Employees' Satisfaction Index (UESI) Questionnaires

In order to further characterize the metro and commuter urban railway stations previously selected, UESI questionnaires were used. UESI questionnaires were based on exploring women's needs and expectation about the railway transport service and infrastructures.

The outline of the UESI questionnaires was designed by TU Dublin based on the CFCs, FCs and IPs identified for the Use Case I. It was composed of two main parts: (i) users' satisfaction of the service and infrastructure design; (ii) socio-demographic characteristics and mobility patterns of the end-users which will be allowed for the presentation of the findings in a disaggregated way regarding the many varieties of passengers. UESI questionnaires were administered face to face and online by the staff of the Spanish and Polish organisations, on the platform of the selected stations to ensure a wide range of participants at different time periods of the day, including peak and off-peak hours, from M16-February 2020 to M24-October 2020.

Then, the outline of the UESI questionnaires was translated in several languages and data were collected online from the general public across partner countries (France, Italy, Poland, Serbia, Spain and UK) in order to provide more robust cross-cultural findings. The number of UESI questionnaires gathered through data collection activities for the Use Case I covers the desired representativeness considering the targeted objective of 800 questionnaires.

Accessibility & Comfort; Safety and Security; Service organisation; and Capability to address service needs were the four main factors of the fairness characteristics that emerged and were used in the interpretation of the data. The following key findings were highlighted:

- Gender showed relevance across many items and significant gender differences could be seen across the questionnaire. Across all data sets, women especially felt less satisfied around safety and security issues than men, and non-binary users even less so.
- There is one statement that has, across all data, sets rated lower than others: "There are quiet or private facilities available to parents for infant feeding if they wish to avail of them", indicating a lack of specific facilities for parents.
- The correlation index found that most questions were not strongly correlated across the 3 data sets, although there were higher correlations (>0.45) around the factors of accessibility and comfort, safety and security and general service satisfaction.
- From the stepwise analysis on linear regression, results show that general satisfaction may be determined by different characteristics in between the Irish Organisation and Spanish and Polish samples. Despite this, all 3 data sets highlighted operational hours and frequency of service, information provided, pricing, facilities and comfort, as well as safety.
- Perceived safety varied greatly across stations in all cases. In the FGC data, users from urban areas are more satisfied with safety while users from rural areas are less satisfied, the opposite was observed in Irish Organisation.
- "Travelling with dependents" and "having a chronic illness/disability" were factors that impacted accessibility and comfort in the Spanish and Polish data set. Ethnicity was a factor for safety and security and caring responsibility was important for accessibility and comfort and in the Polish sample, whilst travel line and income were very important for the Spanish dataset.

- The age group of was most critical of the service provided in Irish sample that was 35-44 years, while in Spanish older people were more critical, depending on the line travelling. The unique services such as the “free travel scheme”, offered to older citizens in Irish sample, and accessibility and services provided by certain lines in Spanish may be the reasons for the discrepancy of results.

2.1.1.4 [Social Media Data](#)

The selected 10 stations from the structured data were further characterized through the analysis of disaggregated Social Media Data collected by the KALIUM tool³ from Twitter Social Network, focusing on: (i) geospatial data; (ii) time-based metadata; (iii) content (hashtags). Social media data was aimed at monitoring the areas surrounding the selected relevant stations and cluster geospatial data. Then, the data set was disaggregated based on the gender of the users through the open-source tool M3Inference⁴. This allowed us to investigate gender difference in the activity of Twitter users, by performing content analysis through hashtags and relevant keywords (for full details of the social media analysis see D4.3)

- For the Spanish Organisation women were more concerned about fares and the environment. Women also mentioned the issues that arose from going to work more often, such as schedule, lines, and journeys. In comparison physical factors such as platforms were more likely to be mentioned by men. Concerns regarding delays and changes to schedules were shown by both men and women. In the transport area the effect of Covid-19 seemed to be that women were more thankful but also concerned by practical issues such as disinfection use while men demonstrated more anger and suspicion.
 - For the Polish Organisation, women again were likely to mention work and referenced schedule issues. Women speak more about people, express more frustration and use more swear words in the case of both ‘autobus’ and tramway. Men were more concerned about other means of transport, like subway, bikes or car as an alternative to the ‘autobus’.
- Dynamic Argumentative Delphi (DAD) Survey

Fairness Characteristics (FCs), as factors influencing on decisions of women when facing the transport system, were identified and classified in 3 levels in a hierarchical model. Results can be found in García-Jiménez, E. et al. (2020).

2.1.1.1 [Dynamic Argumentative Delphi Survey results in summary](#)

Online Dynamic Argumentative Delphi survey questionnaires were used to access the opinion of end-users in order to weight/prioritize the fairness characteristics (FCs), by using the Analytic

³ Napalkova, L., Aragón, P., Robles, J.C.C. (2018). Big data-driven platform for cross-media monitoring. In: Proceedings of IEEE 5th International Conference on Data Science and Advanced Analytics (DSAA), pp. 392–399.

⁴ Wang, Z., Hale, S., Adelani, D. I., Grabowicz, P., Hartman, T., & Jurgens, D. (2019). Demographic Inference and Representative Population Estimates from Multilingual Social Media Data. In Proceedings of World Wide Web Conference (pp. 2056-2067).

Hierarchy Process (AHP), identified through the Thematic Analysis and clustered in a hierarchical model of FCs level 1 and FCs level 2. The DAD questionnaires were gathered from general public using several techniques under the public engagement strategy: an innovative snowball approach designed for complex questionnaires, e-mailing, newsletters and sharing the online surveys via social media.

The outline of the DAD survey questionnaires data was collected from across partner countries, (France, Italy, Poland, Serbia, Spain and UK). in order to provide robust cross-cultural findings to hierarchize the identified CFCs and FCs. After the execution of the data collection campaigns, and according to the Grant Agreement, the number of DAD Survey Questionnaires targeted for the Use Case I are No. 500.

- Safety and security emerged as the FC of level 1 deemed the most relevant both for the aggregated analysis and for all groups analysed in the intersectional analysis, according to DAD surveys. Overcrowding and emergency situations in particular emerged as the main FCs of level 2. Results can be consulted in Poveda-Reyes, S. et al. (2021).

Level 3 FCs were provided with data collected from structured data, observations and UESI questionnaires. A maximum likelihood Bayesian Network was used to weight each level 3 FC.

Weights obtained through the DAD surveys and the AHP analysis for the level 1 and level 2 FCs were multiplied per these weights obtained for the level 3 FCs. This multiplication process was carried out as follows: The weight of each level 3 FC was multiplied by the weight of the level 2 FC on which this level 3 FC depended, and by the weight of the level 1 FC on which the level 2 FC depended.

Final weights, calculated in this way, were normalized and ordered from the highest to the lowest one, achieving a TOP 10 final hierarchy.

An ANOVA analysis was carried out on TOP10 most weighted Fairness Characteristics level 3 in order to assess which characteristics of the Polyhedral Individual (gender, age, incomes, etc...) showed significant differences between their ranges for them.

This TOP10 final hierarchy of level 3 FCs and results from this ANOVA analysis can be found in the Section 8 of the Deliverable 4.3 of Diamond.

It was concluded by the ANOVA analysis carried out after the AHP and the BN analysis that the main profiles that have significant differences are education and household type. The groups that give lower scores are high level education and singles meaning they are the most unsatisfied groups of people.

[2.1.1.2 Considerations from Focus groups and Interviews in Use Case I](#)

A thematic analysis was carried out to report findings of UC-I were questions include;

- What are the key factors affecting women's travel choices?
- How relevant are they in discriminating between different transport modalities?

Analysis observed the objective of increasing the percentage of women using public transport by addressing issues of gender equitable and inclusive planning policies with respect to their needs as users of the public transport service. Coding took into consideration DIAMOND's fairness characteristics (Level 1) i.e., Accessibility of the service, Infrastructure Design plus Safety and Security. Additionally, level 2 FC's were used as sub-themes of Level 1 FC's as assigned in DIAMOND's hierarchy of fairness characteristics for UC-1 with room for emerging themes.

Interviews and focus group consisted of a total of 59 participants with 22 interviews from Ireland, 29 focus group from Poland and 8 focus group from Spain. The samples of all countries comprised of both male and females aged between 25 and above 75 years, but for Spanish sample which consists of only women. Male sample breakdown includes Ireland's with 32% aged between 25 to 44 years and Poland with 55% aged between 18 and 55 years. There are similarities of concerns and needs in relation to the use of public transport highlighted across data from Ireland, Spain and Poland.

Exploratory analysis highlighted the most recurred themes in the Northern sample for 'accessibility of the service' includes Travel & Wayfinding information provision, Service availability and efficiency, Travel Purpose, Level of service at the public transport access point, Ticketing options & fares. Highly emergent themes for this FC's included Operational hours & intervals and Convenience of travel system & process. Similar to the Northern sample, Eastern European data indicated travel purpose as a protruding prior theme, while having Convenience of travel system & process and Fares, affordability and exclusions as new findings. In comparison to the preceding location, Southern European data views overall rating of the service as positive with highly frequent, punctual, reliable and well-connected trains service but suggest improvement on sufficient direct lines for reduced journey times as well as improved frequency on weekend trains. Similar to the north and east, southern participants noted high cost of travel for family and particular zones.

Following the theme infrastructure design viewed universal design as prominent across Northern and Eastern region. Yet furniture and facility was the most referenced level 2 FC's in Northern Europe. Southern collection noted proximity of seats that deters spaces needed by those with personal needs, children or caring responsibilities. In view of safety and security, the most recurred emergent theme common across Northern, Southern and Eastern Europe is Gardi, security or staff personnel noted mostly by women with views of respond time or visible staff in the case of an incident been a concern. Sothern Europe holds views of general rating level of security as positive. Following Harassment and pickpocketing are viewed to reoccur in all locations and affecting experiences of women while using public transport with concerns of feeling less safe noted. Visibility of the surrounding area of the station is referenced mostly in Northern Europe, yet Southern Europe notes the need for light in remote areas/locations.

Analysis of Northern Europe further shows the most recurred themes highlighted by female and those travelling without dependants. Convenience of the travel of the travel system and process noted by demographics which include women and men, participants travelling with and without dependants, participants not living with a dependant and those living with dependant under 5 years of age. Operational hours are viewed referenced by those living with dependant's while garda, security or staff personnel noted by participant travelling with dependants.

2.1.2 Data set and current lessons learnt from Use case II

The objective of the Use Case II is to investigate women’s emotions as passengers of autonomous vehicles. This is aimed at supporting the development of fully automated cars, able to dynamically adapt driving performance to women’s preferences. The goal of Use Case II is to increase the level of acceptance of women towards autonomous driving technology.

The methodology for data collection⁵ for the Use Case II consisted of the following:

- Service and Employers’ Provision Data:
 - Observations based on an experimental investigation of gender driven emotional reactions to autonomous driving performance;
 - UESI questionnaires regarding the opinion of the end-users; ○ Social media data regarding the opinion of the end-users;
- Users and Employees’ Perception Data:
 - DAD survey questionnaires regarding the opinion of the end-users.

Service and Employers’ Provision Data (only Service Provision Data in this case) were focused on a sample of subjects participating in the experimental study managed by IBV-Instituto de Biomecánica (Valencia, Spain) (Observations and UESI questionnaires) and on the opinion of the end-users across several European Countries (France, Italy, Poland, Serbia, Spain and UK). Users and Employees’ Perception Data (only Users Perception Data in this case) were collected focusing on the opinion of the end-users across several European Countries (France, Italy, Poland, Serbia, Spain and UK).

Table 2: overview of data sources collected and analysed for Use case II

Data Typology	Sources	Time Period	Data Set Designer	Data Set Collector
Observations	Experiments in a driving simulator laboratory setting.	M20-M24 (Completed)	IBV.	IBV.
UESI questionnaires	CFCs (Level 1), FCs (Level 2), Influencing Parameters (Level 3).	M20-M24 (Completed)	IBV.	IBV.
Social Media Data	Twitter (disaggregated) data.	M14-M24 (Completed)	EUT.	EUT.
DAD survey questionnaires	CFCs (Level 1), FCs (Level 2).	M15-M18 (Completed)	AITEC.	AITEC, EURECAT, FTTE, G&V, IBV,

⁵ See ‘Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection’

Data Typology	Sources	Time Period	Data Set Designer	Data Set Collector
				TU Dublin, SYS, WAVE, ZTM.

2.1.2.1 Observations

A series of experiments in a simulator laboratory setting were executed to collect data to objectively validate the impact of autonomous vehicles driving experience for female passengers. A series of autonomous driving scenarios were designed considering different environmental, traffic and driving conditions to elicit emotional reactions to participants. The experimental procedure was based on the use of sensors to empirically monitor participants' psychophysiological reactions (i.e., dependent variables). The main objective of the use of the physiological signals was to obtain a reliable estimation of the emotion of the participant based on the distinction between Arousal (emotion activation level) and Valence (qualitative connotation of the emotion) representation of emotional situation⁶. Several sensors for the recording of these signals were used. Additionally, during the experiments, the participant face was recorded in video to facilitate emotion identification associated with facial expression by means of visualization or automatic identification by a specific software. An equilibrated sample of 40 subjects was obtained. The main goal of the designed experimental protocol was the examination of the gender driven identification of stressors related to autonomous driving performance, focusing on the FCs identified through Thematic Analysis.

Depending on the interaction of Scenario and the Gender of the driver the arousal elicited in each scenario suggested that:

For men, comfort scenario elicited the least arousal, and simultaneity the highest. Differences between men and women were found in both scenarios. Comfort scenario elicited less arousal in men than women while simultaneity scenario elicited less arousal in women than men. In the simultaneity scenario a cognitive task was performed by the participant, cognitive effort usually increases the arousal levels. In situations of faster driving the arousal values measured were high while slower driving is associated with lower levels of arousal, as can be expected. During overtakings and the sportive driving the most negative valence elicited to the participants occurred, while more positive values of valence corresponded to slow events.

Emotional state was measured with physiological variables. Scenarios that elicited a higher impact on emotional state are related with a smooth or aggressive driving modes as well as to performing a simultaneous task. These scenarios also saw gender differences having a higher impact. In the comfort scenario (a smoother driving mode) men are significantly less activated (less arousal) than in the rest of scenarios. Thus, we find a clear "relaxing" effect of this scenario for men. Women however experience the same arousal level in the comfort scenario as the other scenarios.

⁶ Lang, Peter J., Margaret M. Bradley, and Bruce N. Cuthbert. 1999. 'International Affective Picture System (IAPS): Instruction Manual and Affective Ratings'. The Centre for Research in Psychophysiology, University of Florida

Compared with the other scenarios, the sport scenario for men is the most negative (lowest self-declared valence), while it is the second highest arousal level scenario. The arousal level in the sport scenario is similar in women and significantly higher than in the comfort scenario, however, women do not consider this scenario to be as negative as men do. For women, comfort and sport scenarios have the same level of self-declared valence. Women exhibit a lower activation level and assess more positively in the simultaneity scenario than men do.

2.1.2.2 [UESI Questionnaire](#)

UESI questionnaires were focused on the satisfaction of the end-users related to autonomous vehicles. The outline of UESI questionnaires was composed by two main parts. The first is focused on profiling the socio-demographic characteristics and mobility patterns of the end-users and was administrated before the execution of the experiments. The second part was focused on evaluating the users' satisfaction regarding the autonomous driving performance experienced through the simulator. A total of 50 UESI questionnaires were collected. Then, the outline of the UESI questionnaires was translated in English and data were collected online from

The general public across partner countries in order to provide robust cross-cultural findings to further investigate the identified CFCs, FCs and IPs. The number of UESI questionnaires gathered through data collection activities for the Use Case II covers a 230% representativeness considering the targeted objective of 40 questionnaires ⁷.

Key findings were as follows:

- In general, the perception of autonomous vehicles of the sample is positive. The majority of the results were consistent in the assessment of AV's benefits with no differences by the presence of children in the family composition or by gender.
- Some gender differences did emerge. Women indicated greater need to accessibility and mobility, less satisfaction with safety, and placed greater importance of energy efficiency.
- One of the main determinants, after gender, in this sample results is whether women are with/without children. For example, women with children under 12 especially show greater interest in performing simultaneous activities than men and interest in caring for other passengers is higher for men and women with children.
- Willingness to purchase an AV differed pre- and post- experiment. A shift was seen from gender predicting willingness to buy (women less so than men) to individuals with/without children. Before the experiment women with children were less willing to purchase an AV, however after the experiment they were the group with highest level of agreement with the statement (excluding cost).

2.1.2.3 [Social Media](#)

From Twitter Social Network, a series of disaggregated social media data were collected, focusing on their content (hashtags) to retrieve data from the Twitter streaming API in real time (from M12-December 2019 to M24-October 2020) across partner countries in order to provide more

⁷ See 'Deliverable 2.1 Use case definition'

robust cross-cultural findings (about 1 million of Tweets in total) The KALIUM tool⁸ was used. The dataset was disaggregated considering the gender of the users through the open-source tool M3Inference⁹. This tool relies on a deep learning model trained on multilingual data to infer gender of users based on the username, short bio text and profile picture. This allowed to investigate gender difference in the activity of Twitter users, by performing content analysis through hashtags and relevant keywords.

The case study about the use of AV found that women are more concerned with social impact, social context and feelings while men tend to focus more on aspects related to technology and business. Women tend to use more negative language, using fewer positive words related to business and innovation and a more negative tone. Positive words that women did use tended to be in relation to social and daily life.

2.1.2.4 DAD Survey

Fairness Characteristics (FCs), as factors influencing on decisions of women when facing the transport system, were identified and classified in 3 levels in a hierarchical model. Results can be found in García-Jiménez, E. et al. (2020). The goal of data collection through the online DAD survey questionnaires is to get the opinion of end-users in order to weight/prioritize, by using the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), the fairness characteristics (FCs) (Level 2) identified through the Thematic Analysis and clustered in a hierarchical model of FCs level 1 and FCs level 2. The outline of the DAD-Dynamic Argumentative Delphi survey questionnaires¹⁰ was defined by AITEC, considering the CFCs and FCs identified through the Thematic Analysis. The online DAD provided responses gathered from the general public using several techniques under the public engagement strategy: an innovative snowball approach designed for complex questionnaires, e-mailing, newsletters and spreading the online surveys in the social media. Data were collected from across partner countries in order to provide robust cross-cultural findings to hierarchize the identified CFCs and FCs.

116 DAD surveys filled found *Trust in technology, public health, non-monetary costs, emissions and vehicle behaviour* were the five most important Fairness characteristics identified by the responders, respectively.

The results reveal that:

The ranking of high-level fairness characteristics analysis showed:

⁸ Napalkova, L., Aragón, P., Robles, J.C.C. (2018). Big data-driven platform for cross-media monitoring. In: Proceedings of IEEE 5th International Conference on Data Science and Advanced Analytics (DSAA), pp. 392–399.

⁹ Wang, Z., Hale, S., Adelani, D. I., Grabowicz, P., Hartman, T., & Jurgens, D. (2019). Demographic Inference and Representative Population Estimates from Multilingual Social Media Data. In Proceedings of World Wide Web Conference (pp. 2056-2067).

¹⁰ See 'Deliverable 3.3 Report on data collection campaigns.

- For all the profiles analysed, *Public health* is revealed as the most relevant factor in the Top 5 criteria. It is the most important one for women travelling with dependents, low wage women earners and those who have felt discriminated for their appearance on public transport.
- Another relevant factor tends to be *safety and security* (except for women that reported experiencing discrimination and selected the *environment*) and the *design options* is the last factor in the top 5.
- *Mobility* is more preferred than *environment*, for women travelling with dependents
- The binomial *environment* and *economy* are favoured over *safety & security*, for women who experienced discrimination.
- The *economy* is more weighted than the *environment* for non-urban women whereas the *environment* is more relevant than *economy*, for women with annual incomes lower than 21K€

Women who experienced discrimination were the only ones to include *Congestion* in the top 5 criteria.

The main characteristics when considering key characteristics having an impact on their acceptance of AV for future scenarios were:

- *Simultaneity* allows for the performance of more than one task at the same time because the car drives by itself. For women living in rural areas, it is the most important factor. This could be due to the longer distances to travel to carry out their daily tasks such as going to work shopping or bringing their children to or from school.
- The main factor considered important by women with low incomes is *non-monetary cost*.
- The main factor for the global population, for women travelling with dependents and for women who experienced discrimination on public transport is *Public health*, factor linked with driving without stress and being relaxed during the trips.
- Similar to the present scenario, the ranking of the factors is different regarding the profile analysed, but *non-monetary cost* is repeated for all apart from women travelling with dependents and *Public Health* except for women living in rural areas.

A full picture of this analysis is provided in the paper published about it by Poveda-Reyes, S. et al. (2021)

In this Use case II, Level 3 FCs were provided with data collected from observations (through the simulator) and UESI questionnaires. A maximum likelihood Bayesian Network was used to weight each level 3 FC.

Weights obtained through the DAD surveys and the AHP analysis for the level 1 and level 2 FCs were multiplied per these weights obtained for the level 3 FCs. This multiplication process was carried out as follows: The weight of each level 3 FC was multiplied by the weight of the level 2 FC on which this level 3 FC depended, and by the weight of the level 1 FC on which the level 2 FC depended.

Final weights, calculated in this way, were normalized and ordered from the highest to the lowest one, achieving a TOP 10 final hierarchy.

An ANOVA analysis was carried out on TOP10 most weighted Fairness Characteristics level 3 in order to assess which characteristics of the Polyhedral Individual (gender, age, incomes, etc...) showed significant differences between their ranges for them.

This TOP10 final hierarchy of level 3 FCs and results from this ANOVA analysis can be found in the Section 8 of the Deliverable 4.3 of Diamond.

2.1.2.5 [Qualitative data analysis considerations for Use case II](#)

Discussion about qualitative information of women’s attitudes towards autonomous vehicles is presented in Chapter 2.2 of the present deliverable.

2.1.3 [Data set and Current lessons learnt from Use case III](#)

The objective of the Use Case III is to investigate women’s needs as users of bike sharing services. This is aimed at supporting the development of policies for gender-equitable bike sharing fleet management. The goal of the Use Case III is to increase the percentage of women using bike sharing services.

The methodology for data collection I I for the Use Case III consisted of the following:

- Service and Employers’ Provision Data:
 - Structured data regarding the bike sharing docking stations and the operation of the service;
 - Observations regarding universal design indicators of bike sharing docking stations and their surrounding urban context;
 - UESI questionnaires regarding the opinion of the end-users; and follow up protocol including focus groups and interviews collected in Paris and Edinburgh.
 - Social media data regarding the opinion of the end-users;
- Users and Employees’ Perception Data:
 - DAD survey questionnaires regarding the opinion of the end-users.

Service and Employers’ Provision Data (only Service Provision Data in this case) were collected focusing on the bike sharing docking stations managed by VELIB (Syndicat Mixte Autolib et Velib’ Métropole (Metropolitan Area of Paris, France). Users and Employees’ Perception Data (only Users Perception Data in this case) were collected focusing on the opinion of the end-users across several European Countries (France, Italy, Poland, Serbia, Spain and UK).

Table 3: overview of data sources collected and analysed for Use case III

Data Typology	Sources	Time Period	Data Set Designer	Data Set Collector
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I I See ‘Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection’. 43 See ‘Deliverable 3.3 Report on data collection campaigns’

Structured Data	Open data and proprietary data.	M9-M19 (Completed)	SYS.	SYS, VELIB.
Observations	CFCs (Level 1), FCs (Level 2), Influencing Parameters (Level 3).	M17-M24 (Completed)	ENU, SYS.	G&V
UESI questionnaires and follow up protocol (which includes focus groups and or interviews with users)	CFCs (Level 1), FCs (Level 2), Influencing Parameters (Level 3).	M20-M24 (Completed)	G&V, TU Dublin.	VELIB.
Social Media Data	Twitter (disaggregated) data.	M14-M24 (Completed)	EUT, SYS.	EUT.
DAD survey questionnaires	CFCs (Level 1), FCs (Level 2).	M15-M24 (Completed)	AITEC.	AITEC, EUT, FTTE, G&V, IBV, TU Dublin, SYS, WAVE, ZTM.

2.1.3.1 [Structured Data](#)

Structured data collection was utilised in order to select and characterise a sample of suitable bike sharing docking stations managed by VELIB (who manage 1377 docking stations in total). Structured Open Data were retrieved, sorted and filtered from open data repositories, national geoportals and census databases. Preliminary structured open data analysis was based on Geographic Information Systems (GIS). A series of thematic maps related to the localization and density distribution of datasets were designed to assess the level of accessibility of the bike sharing docking stations managed by VELIB, focusing on territorial data, socio-demographic data, mobility data and bike sharing docking stations network data.

Raw data related to the urban scale were extracted on surrounding census section around each docking station. Data were post-processed through:

1. Density-based calculation on buffer areas;
2. Normalization of values (z values in a range between 0 and 1);
3. Weighted formulas of normalized values to prioritize certain indicators.

The proposed approach allowed the calculation of territorial data index (TDI), sociodemographic data index (SDDI) and mobility data index (MDI). Quintile frequency distribution of results allowed the identification of positively relevant stations belonging to the highest quintile and negatively relevant stations belonging to the lowest quintile. The proposed approach for structured open data collection and analysis allowed the identification of a short list of docking stations, characterized by positively and negatively relevant fairness characteristics identified in the thematic analysis conducted for Use Case III12

In order to further characterize the shortlisted stations, structured open data were merged with the Structured Proprietary Data provided by VELIB and focused on travel demand data, accessibility and spontaneity, safety and security, social constraints weather and topography.

The proposed approach for structured open data collection allowed the identification of a short list of 20 heterogeneous and non-adjacent docking stations, characterized by positively and negatively relevant fairness characteristics related to the objectives of the Use Case III13. The shortlisted docking stations were further investigated through: (i) structured proprietary data; (ii) onsite observations about universal design indicators; (iii) UESI questionnaires focused on women's needs and expectations; (iv) social media data from Twitter regarding the opinion of the end-users

2.1.3.2 Observations

Onsite observations were aimed at further characterizing the bike sharing docking stations previously selected through structured open data. ENU with the support of SYS designed a checklist, which observations were based on, that used the findings collected from the thematic analysis to evaluate the relevant infrastructure design and surrounding context characteristics related to women's needs as users of bike sharing docking stations. The assessment checklist¹⁴ was based on the CFCs, FCs and IPs identified for the Use Case III which included five main concepts: (i) Accessibility and Spontaneity; (ii) Safety and Security; (iii) Social Constraints; (iv) Weather and Topography; (v) Other. Onsite observations took the form of researchers visually observing the public and recording their findings on paper. Results were organized in a tabular structure based on a collaborative Excel worksheet. In addition, some still photo survey of the metro and urban railway stations was carried out as evidence supporting the observation scoring.

The results emphasized that:

- 60% of the docking stations displayed some negative connotations in regard to the percentage of bikes recorded during the observation (depending on docking station capacity), spontaneity of accessing the bike service (the index is for reasons related to the maximum number of bikes observed at the docking station/ or the minimum number of bikes recorded during the observation) and the number of other public modes of transport

¹² Further information about Structure Open Data analysis are provided in 'Deliverable 4.1 Datasets description'.

¹³ Further information about Structure Open Data analysis are provided in 'Deliverable 4.1 Datasets description'.

¹⁴ See 'Deliverable 3.3 Report on data collection campaigns'

near the docking station. Another observation was that no bikes were reported to have a child seat.

- The observed percentage of female users was assessed, and the characteristics related to public awareness were equally distributed between positive and negative.
- Around 90% of observed docking stations displayed some negative features in relation to separate infrastructure like the lack of a separate cycle infrastructure and/or the presence of a cycle lane nearby the docking station (approx. 200m around)
- Above 40% of docking station had negative features related to perceived personal safety and safe environment

2.1.3.3 [UESI Questionnaire](#)

UESI questionnaires were aimed at further characterizing the bike sharing docking stations previously selected through structured open data. UESI questionnaires were designed to provide data related to women's needs and expectations regarding bike sharing services and infrastructures. The outline of the UESI questionnaires I5 was designed by TU Dublin based on the CFCs, FCs and IPs identified for Use Case III such as cost, safety equipment and local cycling infrastructure and was composed of two main parts: (i) users' satisfaction of the service and infrastructure design; (ii) socio-demographic characteristics and mobility patterns of the end-users which allows us to provide disaggregated data on women users. The main data considered was collected by VELIB in Paris however the on-line questionnaire could be used to responses collected online from the general public across partner countries (France, Italy, Poland, Serbia, Spain and UK) in order to provide more robust cross-cultural findings to further investigate the identified CFCs, FCs and IPs. The number of UESI questionnaires gathered through data collection activities for the Use Case III specific to VELIB covers a 99% representativeness considering the targeted objective of 400 questionnaires I6.

The key findings were:

- Significant gender differences could be seen across the questionnaire. Women felt less satisfied around accessibility and safety and security issues than men across all data sets.
- Most questions were not strongly correlated in the correlation index, however around the factors of accessibility and spontaneity and safety and security there were higher correlations (>0.45).
- Satisfaction for users was positively related to age. Younger respondents (18-44 years) were less critical of bike-sharing systems than older respondents (45-74 years).
- Perception of safety was associated with the volume of traffic. Lower levels of traffic predicated increased perception of safety and consequently user satisfaction. Visibility and adequate lighting at docking stations also gave a predicted increased in sense of security and user satisfaction.

I5 See 'Deliverable 3.3 Report on data collection campaigns'.

I6 See 'Deliverable 2.1 Use case definition'.

- User satisfaction was negatively impacted by absence of accessories for transporting children and carting goods, respondents indicated that provision would increase their level of satisfaction.
- Cycling and bike sharing was, unsurprisingly, significantly impacted by weather conditions, however this could be mitigated by the supply of cycling raincoats to increase user satisfaction.

2.1.3.4 [Social Media](#)

The selected docking stations were further characterized through the analysis of disaggregated social media data collected from Twitter Social Network, focusing on: (i) geospatial data; (ii) time-based metadata; (iii) content (hashtags). The KALIUM tool¹⁷ was used to retrieve data from the Twitter streaming API in real time and focused on the Metropolitan Area of Paris (France).

The dataset was disaggregated considering the gender of the users through the open source tool M3Inference¹⁸. This allowed the investigation of gender difference in the activity of Twitter users, by performing content analysis through hashtags and relevant keywords.

The analysis showed that the debate on Twitter is quite politicized, both among men and women. For tweets involving the major's name the term "fiasco" was often used by men exhibiting more of an aggressive tone compared to women who often used the term 'merci' or thanks exhibiting a kinder tone.

2.1.3.5 [DAD Survey](#)

The goal of data collection through the online DAD survey questionnaires is to get the opinion of end-users in order to weight/prioritize, by using the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), the fairness characteristics (FCs) identified through the Thematic Analysis and clustered in a hierarchical model of FCs level 1 and FCs level 2. The DAD survey collected responses gathered from members of the general public using several techniques under the public engagement strategy such as an innovative snowball approach for complex surveys, e-mailing, newsletters and spreading the online surveys in the social media. The DAD survey questionnaires were collected from across all partner countries in order to provide robust cross-cultural findings to hierarchize the identified CFCs and FCs. 97 DAD surveys were used in the analysis of bicycle sharing for Use case III. Results can be consulted in Poveda-Reyes, S. et al. (2021). Please see deliverable 4.2 for further details.

Factors that participants were more concerned about included weather and topography. People do not have any protection to avoid inclement weather, when riding a bicycle. Riding on rainy, windy or snowing days is not very comfortable. Another factor was *Family responsibilities*. Bicycle

¹⁷ Napalkova, L., Arag' on, P., Robles, J.C.C. (2018). Big data-driven platform for cross-media monitoring. In: Proceedings of IEEE 5th International Conference on Data Science and Advanced Analytics (DSAA), pp. 392–399.

¹⁸ Wang, Z., Hale, S., Adelani, D. I., Grabowicz, P., Hartman, T., & Jurgens, D. (2019). Demographic Inference and Representative Population Estimates from Multilingual Social Media Data. In Proceedings of World Wide Web Conference (pp. 2056-2067).

sharing services rarely provide bicycles adapted for the companions and so there is no option to use them for people travelling with dependents, such as children or the elderly.

As a mean of transport bike sharing is considered a healthy and eco-friendly option and this could be a reason why women indicate the increase the *public awareness campaigns on the benefits of cycling*. A strong relation between bike-sharing and social and political issues was also highlighted on social media, especially by women. If the many benefits cycling is understood people will be more inclined to increase their use.

Level 3 FCs were provided with data collected from structured data, observations and UESI questionnaires. A maximum likelihood Bayesian Network was used to weight each level 3 FC.

Weights obtained through the DAD surveys and the AHP analysis for the level 1 and level 2 FCs were multiplied per these weights obtained for the level 3 FCs. This multiplication process was carried out as follows: The weight of each level 3 FC was multiplied by the weight of the level 2 FC on which this level 3 FC depended, and by the weight of the level 1 FC on which the level 2 FC depended.

Final weights, calculated in this way, were normalized and ordered from the highest to the lowest one, achieving a TOP 10 final hierarchy.

An ANOVA analysis was carried out on TOP10 most weighted Fairness Characteristics level 3 in order to assess which characteristics of the Polyhedral Individual (gender, age, incomes, etc...) showed significant differences between their ranges for them.

For the top 10 Fairness Characteristics presented in the most granular level the living environment is the characteristic of the Polyhedral Individual with most significant differences, concerning the bike sharing services.

The top 10 level 3 Fairness Characteristics (FC) for Use Case III saw the following preferences:

- Public awareness campaign on the benefits of cycling
- Better and safe cycling facilities to encourage cycling
- Lowering traffic speeds on roads with on-road cycle lanes
- Safe cycle routes for cycling with children
- Bikes with child seats and trailers for carrying kids and carting cargo
- Cycling rain Poncho
- Avoid hilly terrain in the development of cycle networks where possible

Availability of end-of-trip cycling facilities

- The analysis of the characteristics of the Polyhedral Individual that reveal significant differences in the preferences articulated in the user satisfaction questionnaire. Some of which are as follows:
- The responses to the FC in relation to the possibility of bikes with child seats and trailers for carrying goods
 - Living environment (most unsatisfied were those living in suburban areas)

- Disability (most unsatisfied were people with an illness or disability)
- Travel with dependents (most unsatisfied were those who travel with dependents)
- Education (most unsatisfied were those with a master degree or above)
- The responses to the FC in relation to better and safe cycling facilities to encourage cycling varied depending on:
 - Living environment (most unsatisfied were those living in urban areas)
- The responses to the FC in relation to lowering traffic speeds on roads with on-road cycle lanes varied depending on:
 - Income (most unsatisfied were those who earn 51,000-70,999€)

2.1.3.6 [Considerations from Focus groups and interviews in Use Case III](#)

The opportunities and benefits of the bike-sharing schemes raised by interviewees were found to be the feeling of freedom, comfort and convenience, as they are generally regarded as less restrictive, a quicker way to travel and very convenient. The interviewees however also pointed to challenges faced by these types of schemes. These challenges limit bike-sharing schemes portion of the urban model split and hinders growth. This is especially true for women users. Interviewees also suggested measures to tackle the outlined barriers to ensure more women use the schemes and general growth.

The majority of interviewees either had practical or management experience or have used bike-sharing services. Within the interview participants explained the reasons for why they cycle and how they benefit from it. In general bike-sharing was chosen for commuting, leisure, environmentally friendly and need to be active. It was also the opinion of the interviewees that cost of hiring, freedom from the responsibility of storage and maintenance, convenient impacted the level of bike-sharing use. For tourist and visitors bike-sharing is a great mobility option for completing the last part of a mix-mode journey.

The perceived barriers to the use of bike-sharing services according to the interviewees included bikes unavailability, unsafe infrastructure, safety, shortage of stations and lack of appropriate bike accessories. These barriers may limit the use of the bike-sharing schemes. A number of suggestions and recommendations address these barriers were similarly made to increase the ridership of bike-sharing services and can be found in D4.2 section 3.3.

2.1.4 [Data set and Current lessons learnt from Use case IV](#)

The objective of the Use Case IV is to investigate the women's needs as employees in the transport sector. The goal of the Use Case IV is to assess the key factors regarding fairness and inclusiveness of employment in different positions and roles in the transport sector and help to increase the percentage of women working on-site and off-site in specific male dominated roles in railway, freight transport and the logistics sectors.

The methodology for data collection¹⁹ for Use Case IV consisted of the following:

- Service and Employers’ Provision Data:
 - Structured data: regarding percentage of women involved in professional jobs related to transport sector in several EU Countries. In different job roles, data regarding their career progressions, their job opportunities training, conditions of employment etc.
 - UESI questionnaires: regarding the opinion of the employees;
- Users and Employees’ Perception Data: n
 - DAD survey questionnaires regarding the opinion of the end-users.
 - Semi-structured online Interviews with employees

Online semis structured interviews

Online semis structured interviews (Scotland, Ireland, Spain and Poland)

Online Focus groups (Poland)

Service and Employers’ Provision Data (only Employers Provision Data in this case) were provided by the Human Resources Department of FGC-Ferrocarrils de la Generalitat de Catalunya (Province of Barcelona, Spain), RINA-Rina Services spa (Genoa, Italy) and ZTM Miasto Stoleczne Warszawa (Warsaw Metropolitan Area, Poland). Users and Employees’ Perception Data (only Employees Perception Data in this case) were collected focusing on the opinion of women and men involved in professional jobs related to transport sector across several European Countries (Poland, Spain and Ireland).

Table 4: overview of data sources collected and analysed for Use case IV

Data Typology	Sources	Time Period	Data Designer	Set	Data Collector	Set
Structured Data	Open data and proprietary data.	M9-M24 (Partial data)	STIR, Dublin.	TU	FGC, STIR, TU Dublin ZTM.	
UESI questionnaires and follow up protocol (which	CFCs (Level 1), FCs (Level 2), Influencing Parameters (Level 3).	M19-M24 completed	G&V, STIR, TU Dublin.		FGC, ZTM.	

¹⁹ See ‘Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection’

Data Typology	Sources	Time Period	Data Set Designer	Data Set Collector
includes focus groups and or interviews with users)				
DAD survey questionnaires	CFCs (Level 1), FCs (Level 2).	M15-M24 (Completed)	AITEC.	AITEC, EUT, FTTE, G&V, IBV, TU Dublin, SYS, WAVE, ZTM.
Qualitative Semi Structured Interviews		Completed		TUDublin STIR ZTM FGC EURECAT
Focus Groups		Completed		FGC EURECAT ZTM

2.1.4.1 [Structured Data](#)

Structured data collection was aimed at characterizing the level of participation of women to on-site and off-site professional jobs related to the transport sector (railway, freight transport and logistics sectors). On-site professional jobs were defined as those related to administrative and office management support in transport departments, operators for warehouses rail and maintenance technicians etc. Off-site professional jobs were defined as those including drivers of short and long distances. Structured Open Data collection was performed by STIR and TU Dublin using historical series of open data collected from Euro Stats which included data from across several European Countries and through Structured Proprietary Data provided by partners at FGC, RINA and ZTM. The goal of structured data collection was to depict the current level of participation of women in the wider transport sector and were collected considering the CFCs, FCs and IPs identified through Thematic Analysis²⁰, based on level I CFC's of job characteristics, personal circumstances, individual characteristics and socio-economic conditions.

2.1.4.2 [UESI Questionnaire](#)

UESI questionnaires were designed to highlight the barriers and needs related to the participation of women in professional jobs related to the transport sector across the EU. The outline of UESI questionnaires²¹ was composed in two main parts. The first is focused on profiling the socio-

²⁰ See 'Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection'

²¹ See 'Deliverable 3.3 Report on data collection campaigns'.

demographic characteristics and career profiles of participants employees in transport sector. The second is focused on evaluating employees' satisfaction regarding job conditions and employability. Data were collected online from general public across partner countries in order to provide robust cross cultural findings to further investigate the identified CFCs, FCs and IPs.

The key findings were:

- One relevant predictor of employees' perception related to organization inclusiveness was gender. Women often had a lower level of satisfaction with some of the statements, for example levels and jobs in transport related to the context, balance between genders across occupations and satisfaction with how the context employees living in supports fairness and inclusiveness of women in transport.
- The majority of the sample was female limiting examination of gender differences in Eastern European data set. Strong correlations were seen between income and environment, and organisational inclusive satisfaction. The country in which the data was collected have state funded provision for childcare for children over 3 years of age, therefore this may have impacted the fact that affordable childcare services was not highlighted as a relevant issue.
- Women in the Northern European data set signalled less agreement with statements related to fairness and gender balance and acceptance of women in their organisation and in the transport sector of their country. Affordable childcare services was one of the greatest needs expressed by women as well as expenses/support for traveling to work. While fairness and inclusivity of women in transport in their country and of women employees in their organisation saw women rate less satisfaction.
- There were only a few gender differences in the Southern European Data set, overall. Women indicated less agreement with women's acceptance by male colleagues in the workplace. A significant difference was seen relating to satisfaction with organisational inclusiveness through job level/type and whether you had children or not.

2.1.4.3 [DAD Survey](#)

The goal of data collection through the online DAD survey questionnaires was to access the opinion of end-users in order to weight/prioritize, the fairness characteristics (FCs), by using the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), identified through the Thematic Analysis and clustered in a hierarchical model of FCs level 1 and FCs level 2. The questionnaires were completed by the general public using several techniques under the public engagement strategy such as an innovative snowball approach specially designed for complex questionnaires, e-mailing, newsletters and sharing the online surveys via the social media. Data were collected from across partner countries (France, Italy, Poland, Serbia, Spain and UK) in order to provide robust cross-cultural findings to hierarchize the identified CFCs and FCs.

Caring and parenting responsibilities were the most highlighted factor even for those profiles that do not necessarily have children or elderly relatives in the household type according to the DAD surveys carried out. The limitation of taking care of those relatives that need them when accessing a job is something people are very aware of in general.

The most relevant factor obtained after analysing the employee's perception data was *having the opportunity to change shifts and to reducing the working time to those with small children*, the flexibility

of the work is important as it allows for better organization of their daily life tasks, e.g. to go to the doctor or to take care of themselves in case they were ill, etc.

Significant differences according to the education level, and for users living with dependents was highlighted through the ANOVA analysis carried out after the AHP and the BN analysis. The groups expressing the lowest levels of satisfaction were medium level education and those living with dependents. A full picture of all these results can be consulted in section 8 of the Deliverable 4.3 of Diamond.

As stated above the objective of Use Case IV is to investigate the barriers and facilitators to women's employment in the transport sector, with the aim of increasing the participation of female employees across the sector. In order to provide data which met with the ideal type of the polyhedral individual (as set out in D2.1) across all roles in the transport sector and be representative of the DIAMOND inclusion diamond (as set out in D2.1) semi-structured interviews were developed by partners at TUDublin and STIR for Use Case IV in order to explore the experiences of women who had worked or were currently working in the transport sector (for a full description please D4.2 section 3.2).

A top-down approach is being taken to the data analysis with the data firstly being divided by case nodes which will identify each country, gender, age and all other demographic information of participants to allow us to provide a descriptive analysis based on disaggregated data for women and the association between different socio-economic and psycho-ethno-anthropological characteristics including different objective and subjective measures as set out in the grant agreement (P19/42)

2.1.4.4 Considerations from Focus Groups and Interviews in Use Case IV

Use Case IV specifically considers the key factors regarding fairness and inclusiveness of employment for women across the transport sector and help to increase the percentage of women working off-site and on-site in that sector. UC IV set out to answer whether different job characteristics or contextual factors effect female employability and gender balance and what key factors influence job choice for women in the transport sector.

The research data suggested that **there is job segregation within the transport system** and that it does **impact gender balance and female employability**. The job segregation, according to some interviewees, has come from historical or more traditional ideas of 'men's jobs' and 'women's jobs'. Across the sector the dominance of male employees was evident.

In order to address the issue of gender balance some companies were involved in attending schools, universities, colleges and job fairs to promote female employment in their transport company. This was to provide more of an **awareness and education around jobs in the transport sector**. Many interviewees suggested that more education and communication around the roles available within the transport sector and their suitability for women is necessary to encourage an increase in the number of women in transport job roles. Many pointed out examples of women in transport groups that support and positively impact women employees and help promote a more gender-balanced industry.

When looking at the gender balance and female employability with regard to vacancy characteristics the interviewees suggested shift work, working hours and opportunity for progressions as hindrance. While interviewees indicated that selection preferences, **recruitment and selection procedures** and discrimination all play a role in gender balance. While in regards to legal factors or policy the research data noted that they should in theory promote fairness in the workplace but actually are just a 'tick box' action.

The research also highlighted that **appropriate female facilities were lacking** meaning the working environment was discriminatory for women. The reason behind this lack in facilities was deemed to be as a result of the industries job segregation. The data did suggest also that many interviewees **experienced sexism and discrimination at work.**

In general, across the sector and in the different locations organisations did not specifically target women for employment opportunities, as they did not want that in itself to be discriminatory and wanted the right person to get the job regardless of gender. However, organisations did have strategies such as diversity targets and equality plans. Many interviewees stated that their company does actively seek to retain their employees. The data disclosed many points in terms of training provision and gender balance. Generally there is equality of access to training that is usually paid for by the employer and there is often training designed specifically for women.

Fairness in the transport industry according to many of the interviewees is about flexibility, e.g., flexible working hours, however the data suggests that a lot of jobs in the transport industry would not be compatible with that type of flexibility. A lot of the interviewees also agreed that many roles require shift work and unsociable working hours, while this may not impact those who do not have children it greatly impacts those who do. While it was agreed that it would be discriminatory to suggest that women should provide the majority of childcare the interviewees recognised that the reality is that they often do. The evidence from the research data did indicate that caring/parenting responsibilities impact upon gender balance and women's employability in the transport industry.

The research data on FC skills in terms of gender balance or female employment did not provide many insights. Generally the data indicated that **specialist skills or educational level impacts the level or role undertaken by women** but a lot of the front line or operational roles are a learned skill within the organisation and women apprentices numbers are low. The interviews and focus group discussions found no data on the FCs of health status and wellbeing, economic deprivation residential location/work distance transport access to work place or for individual characteristics, such as adaptability, attitude to work in terms of adaptability and attitude to work.

In terms of increasing the participation of women employed in the transport system a key factor is the **concept of job segregation**, i.e. jobs for only men or only women. Across all the interviews the industry appeared to be still viewed and experienced as a male dominated industry. Three main themes emerged when discussing understanding of why girls and women are still underrepresented. They were that they were attracting women to the industry, recruitment processes, and processes put in place to retain women employees, all falling under FC demand factors. It was noted that **many women and young girls are not aware of the variety of roles within the transport sector and that more effort is needed to engage them.**

However, during discussion in focus groups and interviews targeted recruitment of female employees was regarded as adding ‘a target’ to the backs of women.

A factor that was seen to impact in female career choices was having **female role models or mentors in the workplace**, some interviewees in senior roles agreed and claimed that they believed it was their responsibility to support any women who might want to follow in their footsteps.

The question “Are current employment practices in your country fair for women?” was asked to determine the impact of employment policies and law across different partner states (Ireland, UK, Poland and Spain). The responses indicated that while there are many policies in place currently they are not utilised consistently across all organisations and that these policies are often developed by business men or lawyers who do not fully understand the experiences of women on the frontline, with the majority of responses declaring that more needs to be done.

Lack of female facilities and was one of the largest findings that emerged from the data to impact women’s career choices in the transport industry. Many interviewees highlighted that there was a lack of space for women, they had to share a toilet with men or use the disabled toilets which in turn impacts the access of disabled people to their toilets.

In terms of equality of opportunity for women to access training provision, there was no difference seen compared to men. In terms of railways and road haulage, all drivers must legally have the same training in order to be employed.

The data related to the FC “terms and conditions” suggested that across countries and transport organisations was equal pay not a key factor as it tended to be covered by legislation, meaning women and men are paid the same for the same job. However under this FC caring or parenting responsibilities was seen as a key factor for women’s career choices. Flexible working hours and their provision was seen across all employment FCs.

Data from the **safety and security theme** included the provision of PPE designed for women and not unisex, other provisions that arose were lone working and training in protection and awareness. From the data it is seen that the majority of transport organisations are still providing unisex PPE (as regarded by them), which some frontline interviewees described as “designed for men”.

The **perceived reaction of male colleagues to having women alongside them in the transport sector** can also be an important factor in women’s career choices. Many interviewees working across the transport sector reported this, frontline managers, senior managers and directors supporting the idea that negative male attitudes towards women employees can still be found, even in the board rooms of the transport sector.

The **low numbers of women in STEM or technical subjects** that undermine many transport sector roles has an impact on educational attainment as a factor for women when considering a career in the transport sector. Many Organisations stated that in order to address this they now have a presence at **open days or career days in schools and colleges to encourage young girls to enter into the sector**.

The focus groups and interviews saw no data sets emerge from the FCs economic deprivation, transport access to work place, health status and wellbeing and effects of demographics (age ethnicity etc.). They also weren't seen in terms of adaptability and attitude to work but there are themes that emerged based on flexibility of working location and hours and the impact of shift work.

The findings that emerged from the data that were not before accounted for in the FCs that influence women's choice of career included the individual personality or characteristics that a woman may possess. More on this can be read in deliverable 4.2

Possibilities for Change

In regard to women's employment in the transport sector and the factors that influence women's career choices in respect to employment the interviewees did acknowledge that there was a need for change in order to support women as employees in the sector. These changes will also help to encourage more women to join the sector. These changes are discussed in del 4.2.

2.2 Overview of Diamond and the SUaAVE Project, Women's attitudes towards autonomous vehicles

DIAMOND's use case on autonomous vehicles investigates women's needs as drivers and passengers of autonomous vehicles, to boost women's acceptance of them. In parallel, SUaAVE project (grant agreement N° 814999) is working on the development of a psychological acceptability model with the intention to explain public acceptability of connected autonomous vehicle (CAV) among different types of user groups within the EU, led by RUG University.

In SUaAVE, with the goal of collecting data from European population to feed the acceptability model, a large-scale survey was conducted in April 2020. In this survey, all potential psychological factors influencing acceptability of CAV were measured to determine their significance and strength.

The results of this action are included in SUaAVE Public deliverable 1.2. "Model and guidelines depicting key psychological factors that explain and promote public acceptability of CAV among different user groups".

The database obtained in SUaAVE large survey has a high value in the exploration of gender differences in CAV acceptance. For this reason, a collaboration between RUG University (SUaAVE partner) and IBV (leader of autonomous vehicle use case in DIAMOND) was performed to make a complementary analysis of this data base to identify women priorities to enhance in CAV perception for boosting women acceptability of CAVs.

2.2.1 SUaAVE Model results relevant for DIAMOND

Sample and acceptability

In this point we included main results of SUaAVE In Public deliverable 1.2. relevant for DIAMOND project due to their contribution in the identification of gender differences for women acceptability enhancement.

SUaaVE acceptance model large scale survey was conducted as an online questionnaire. The final **sample consisted of 3783 participants** in total from 18 to 72 years old, mean of 42.8 years, and is relatively evenly spread (20.7% is 30 or younger, 19.8% is 55 or older). The survey **involved six countries**, the Netherlands (637), the United Kingdom (630), Germany (626), France (625), Spain (637), and Italy (628).

The sample is balanced in gender, 50.9% of the participants are women and 49,1% male. The largest group (37.5%) has a university education or higher, followed by secondary vocational education (25.3%), higher professional education (21.2%), high school (14.9%), and finally elementary school or less (1.1%). In terms of car usage, 92,6% have a driver's license, 72.7% owns a car, 32.2% drives every day, and 13% drives rarely (a couple of times a month or less) and 0.9% (34 participants) have at least one physical disability that prevented them from driving.

The CAV acceptability in the sample was directly estimated with the degree of agreement with the statement “The use of connected automated vehicles is acceptable” in a scale from 1- Completely disagree to 7- Completely agree. The mean **CAV acceptability value is 4.7**, meaning the participants were slightly positive towards CAV. There exist significant differences by gender (controlling age and education level). **Men acceptance is 0.27 higher than women.**

Impact of CAV perceived characteristics on acceptability

According to SUaaVE results, the CAV attributes are the strongest predictors in SUaaVE acceptability model. Attributes are seven distinct **perceived characteristics of CAV and reflect the overall perception** of AV use:

1. ***Perceived safety. The belief the vehicle will be safe***
2. ***Perceived convenience. The belief the vehicle will meet the user's driving needs***
3. ***Perceived pleasure. The belief driving in AVs will be pleasant***
4. ***Perceived control. The belief one will have control over the vehicles' behaviour***
5. ***Perceived status – enhancement. The belief owing or driving AVs will increase one's status***
6. ***Perceived environmental sustainability. The belief CAV will be environmentally friendly***
7. ***Trust in CAV technology. The belief the vehicle will behave as intended***

Each of these seven perceived characteristics were defined by 3 statements. Participants, among other questions have to evaluate the degree of agreement of all the statements related CAV perceived characteristics to which they could agree or disagree (7-point Likert scales), the importance given to these seven perceived characteristics, questions related with CAV acceptance, capability of future use and driver profile.

After, a linear regression was run with all assessments of the seven perceived characteristics (mean of three statements rating per characteristic) predicting acceptability together. This model was significant, $F(df = 7, 3764) = 856.891, p < .001, R^2 = .614$.

All **perceived characteristics, except perceived status-enhancement, were significantly positively associated with acceptability of CAV**. The results indicate that the strongest predictors ($\beta > 0,2$) are Safety, Convenience, and Environmental Sustainability.

Table 5: Regression Coefficient of perceived characteristics in acceptability prediction

PERCEIVED CHARACTERISTICS	Coefficient β
Control**	0.035
Pleasure***	0.127
Safety***	0.300
Convenience	0.256
Trust in technology***	0.104
Status-Enhancement	-0.016
Environmental Sustainability***	0.200

** = significant at the .01 level, *** = significant at the .001 level.

2.2.2 Perception of CAV, importance of perceived characteristics and gender differences

The perception of CAV of the sample (in a 1 to 7 scale) is shown in Table 2. With the mean assessment of CAV perceived characteristics and gender differences. **Environmental Sustainability, Trust and Convenience of use are the characteristics better perceived, and Pleasure of driving, Control over the vehicle's behavior and Status-enhancement are the worst perceived with a slightly negative perception, below 4.**

For all characteristics the gender factor is significant (regression analyses controlled for age and education level to find differences between men and women) except for "pleasure".

Table 6: Mean assessment perceived characteristics and impact of factor women against men

Perception of CAV characteristics	Mean	β : Women
Perceived control***	3.670	-0.204
Perceived pleasure	3.912	Ni sig
Perceived safety***	4.133	-0, 272
Perceived convenience***	4.249	-0, 338
Trust in CAV technology***	4.378	-0,333

Perceived status-enhancement***	3.670	-0,303
Perceived of environmental sustainability***	4,480	-0.178

** = significant at the .01 level, *** = significant at the .001 level.

Women scored significantly lower on almost all perceived characteristics except “pleasure” with no difference among genders. The highest differences among genders are in the perception of Convenience of Use, Trust, and Status Enhancement being the last the one with the lowest perception for women in comparison to men’s perception.

Aside from asking participants how they perceived CAV, they were also asked to indicate how important each perceived characteristic was to them. In the importance ratings (Table 3) **Safety, Control and Trust were assessed as the most important perceived characteristics for both genders.** Status-enhancement is not considered important with an importance rating of 3,22 below neutrality.

Regression analyses were conducted to find differences between men and women on the importance of perceived characteristics of CAV (controlling age and education level). Results can be seen in Table 7 below.

Table 7: Mean Importance of perceived characteristics and impact of factor women against men

Importance of CAV characteristics	Mean	β: Women
Importance of control***	6,07	0,272
Importance of pleasure**	5,21	0,139
Importance of safety***	6,45	0,151
Importance of convenience***	5,63	0,200
Importance of trust in CAV technology***	6,07	0,164
Importance of status-enhancement***	3,22	-0,257
Importance of environmental sustainability***	5,61	0,331

** = significant at the .01 level, *** = significant at the .001 level.

The gender factor is significant for the assessment of the importance of all perceived characteristics. **Women tend to give greater importance to all characteristics than men, except for status-enhancement that is rated lower.**

The **highest differences** in importance between genders are **ENVIRONMENTAL sustainability**, followed by **CONTROL**. In both cases women consider them more important than men.

2.2.3 DIAMOND-SUAAVE collaboration for further analysis for women acceptance enhancement

Sample and gender differences in driving profiles

The goal of DIAMOND-SUAAVE collaboration was identifying how to enhance women CAV perception that impact acceptability. For this purpose, the analysis focused on the opinion of current drivers, the biggest subsample of SUaaVE sample (92,5%), with **3497 EU drivers** from 18 to 72 years old homogenously distributed in the six EU counties and in gender (1751 men and 1746 women).

Regarding the driving frequency (Figure 1), the percentage of women driving “Every day” or “Almost every day” (63,9%) is almost 10% lower than in men (73,9%). Additionally, Women who never or almost never drive are 9,7% respect 6,2% of men.

Figure 1: Driving Frequency among genders

For both genders, ownership is the most extended access to a car with a higher percentage in men population (women: 76%, men: 83%) and more women share a car with a family member (women: 17%, men: 10%). The percentage of women without a car are slightly higher than for men. (women: 7%, men: 6%) and the use of car-sharing is very low for both genders (women: 0,7%, men: 0,7%).

Finally, regarding the use of in-vehicle technology in the sample (Figure 2), women use all technologies less frequently than men.

Figure 2: In-vehicle technology use among genders

Acceptability and potential use per country

Mean acceptance ratings among genders and by countries are represented in Figure 3, scale from 1 to 7. The acceptability in Italy and Spain are the highest among all the countries, on the other side The Nederland's and France show the lowest acceptability values.

Figure 3: Acceptability by country among genders

Acceptability rating for women is lower than for men in all countries. On average, acceptability is 4,57 for women and 4,81 for men in the scale from 1 to 7. The Netherlands and Germany have the lowest women acceptability followed by UK. Germany shows the highest differences in acceptability among genders.

The perception of ability to drive an AV vehicle in the future was estimated with the degree of agreement with the statement “I will be able to drive a connected automated vehicle when they become available” in a scale from 1- Completely disagree to 7- Completely agree.

Figure 4: Perception of ability to drive a CAV by country among genders

On average in the sample, the agreement with this statement was 4,3. The Italian population has the highest perception of ability to drive an AV vehicle and The Netherlands the lowest.

The perception of the ability to drive in the future a CAV is lower for women than men in all countries. The Netherlands and Germany present the highest differences among genders and the lowest values for women population and together with France and UK, women population have shown a disagreement with statement (score<4).

Analysis of CAV perception for acceptability enhancement among genders

To identify priorities on CAV perception enhancement to improve acceptability for women and men, an analysis was made to further explore the perceived characteristics of CAV among genders that **reflect the overall perception**.

Each of these seven perceived characteristics, as explained before, were defined by 3 statements. Participants must evaluate the degree of agreement of all the statements related CAV perceived characteristics to which they could agree or disagree (7-point Likert scales).

For these ratings, the correlation with acceptability was calculated with Pearson correlation, all coefficients are significant with a p-values > 0,05 (for two-sided tests).

Table 8: Pearson correlation coefficient with acceptability (in bolds statements with the biggest differences among genders)

Statements for the assessment of Perceived characteristics	CORRELATION WITH ACCEPTABILITY	
	WOMEN	MEN
Driving a CAV would be convenient, it would make my journeys more efficient.	0.658	0.668
A connected automated car would be safe.	0.634	0.617
Connected automated driving would be enjoyable.	0.617	0.596
Driving in a CAV would be pleasurable.	0.611	0.582
I would trust a CAV to behave as intended	0.600	0.600
CAVs would meet my driving needs.	0.598	0.571
I would be in control when driving in a CAV.	0.564	0.396
Connected automated cars would be more environmentally friendly	0.556	0.524
CAVs would reduce carbon emissions and pollution caused by car traffic.	0.538	0.523
CAV would be convenient, allow to spend time on other things than driving.	0.531	0.581
I trust that CAVs would correctly detect other road users.	0.531	0.522
A CAV would emit less particulates and greenhouse gasses.	0.524	0.511
CAVs would pose minimal risk to its driver, passengers, and other road users	0.450	0.514
A CAV would enhance my social status.	0.442	0.427
I trust the computer systems of CAVs cannot get hacked.	0.413	0.380
I can show who I am when driving a CAV.	0.412	0.361
A CAV would give me the possibility to distinguish myself from others.	0.404	0.396

It is considered that improving the perception of the AV characteristics with a high correlation with acceptability, higher than 0.5, would have a higher impact the acceptability. Thus, perceived characteristics with a higher correlation with acceptability are considered more relevant.

To identify the priorities to enhance acceptability, Figure 5 and Figure 6 represent in the x-axe the perception of the item, the score of agreement with statement from 1 to 7, against its correlation with acceptability in the y-axe for women and men, respectively.

The priorities will be identified by a balance of importance-fulfilment i.e. a high correlation (>0.5) with acceptability and a lower fulfilment or negative perception will be prioritized to be improved to increase CAV perception.

The recommendation is that the degree of perception (fulfilment) for the most relevant characteristics must be improved or in case they are properly perceived, at least, this perception must be maintained over the time.

Figure 5: Women priorities: Axe y: Correlation with acceptability Axe x: Perception assessment

According to this approach, in Figure 5, identified women priorities to be improved in CAV perception to enhance their acceptability are:

1. Connected automated vehicles would meet my driving needs, with a negative assessment (fulfillment <4).
2. I would be in control when driving in a connected automated vehicle, with a negative assessment (fulfillment <4).
3. Driving in a connected automated vehicle would be pleasurable.
4. A connected automated car would be safe.
5. Driving a connected automated vehicle would be convenient, since it would make my journeys more efficient.
6. Driving in a connected automated car would be convenient, since it would allow me to spend my time on other things than driving.
7. Connected automated driving would be enjoyable.
8. I would trust a CAV to behave as intended

For women, the following items are also relevant in acceptability but they are better perceived. The perception of the items should be maintained at this moment or even improved in the future:

- Connected automated cars would be more environmentally friendly than conventional cars.
- Connected automated vehicles would reduce carbon emissions and pollution caused by car traffic.

- A connected automated vehicle would emit less particulates and greenhouse gasses than conventional cars.
- I trust that connected automated vehicles would correctly detect other road users.

According to Figure 6 compared with Figure 5, men in general have a better perception of CAV than women, and they not show a negative perception of any item (fulfilment < 4).

Figure 6: Men priorities: Axe y: Correlation with acceptability Axe x: Perception assessment

For men identified priorities to be improved in CAV perception to enhance their acceptability are:

1. Connected automated vehicles would meet my driving needs.
2. Driving in a connected automated vehicle would be pleasurable.
3. Connected automated driving would be enjoyable.
4. A connected automated car would be safe.

For men, the following items are also relevant in acceptability, but they are better perceived. The perception of the items should be maintained at this moment or even improved in the future:

- I would be in control when driving in a connected automated vehicle.
- Driving a connected automated vehicle would be convenient, since it would make my journeys more efficient.
- Driving in a connected automated car would be convenient, since it would allow me to spend my time on other things than driving.
- I would trust a CAV to behave as intended.
- Connected automated cars would be more environmentally friendly than conventional cars.

- Connected automated vehicles would reduce carbon emissions and pollution caused by car traffic.
- A connected automated vehicle would emit less particulates and greenhouse gasses than conventional cars.
- I trust that connected automated vehicles would correctly detect other road users.

2.2.3.1 Conclusions and women priorities to enhance CAV acceptability

From SUaaVE deliverable results the following conclusions are relevant for DIAMOND project:

- The perceived degree of **Safety, Convenience, and Environmental Sustainability** have the strongest impact on acceptability, followed by **Pleasure**. Enhancing or maintaining a good perception of them should be the focus for manufacturers and marketers to enhance acceptance. Additionally, these attributes could be emphasized in marketing, advertising, and information campaigns.
- Vehicle **Safety, Control and Trust** were considered by the sample the most important characteristics for both genders and control is important notably for women, however, control and trust do not have a high lineal impact on acceptability.
- For both genders, Environmental Sustainability, Trust and Convenience of use are the characteristics best perceived of CAV. **Pleasure of Driving, Control over the vehicle's behavior and Status-Enhancement are negatively perceived.**
- Women perceived worse than men all characteristics except pleasure. The highest differences between genders are in the perception of **Trust, Convenience and Status Enhancement.**

According with these conclusions and the results of DIAMOND-SUaaVE collaboration the main aspects to be improved for enhancing women acceptability, ordered by potential impact:

1. Three aspects related with **Convenience are a priority to be improved notably for women** (meets my needs, efficient for me, and seize the time with simultaneous tasks) to increase acceptance. Convenience has the highest capability predicting acceptability and it is worse perceived by women than men.
2. Relating control, in particular, the item **“perception to be in control when driving”** an AV is a priority to be improved for women as it **has a negative perception (<4)** for them and its relevant for women only.
3. The priority to improve the perception that **“AV would be SAFE” is common for both genders** due to the high correlation with acceptance, but this priority is more important for women as the perceived AV safety is lower. SAFETY is considered important and one with the highest capability predicting acceptability.
4. The priority **to improve Pleasure is common for both genders**. PLEASURE have a high capability predicting acceptability, but it is not considered as one of the most important characteristics. The perception of pleasure is low for both genders.
5. **Environmental Sustainability** it is the best perceived characteristic, thus, this perception must be **maintained or even improved to guarantee** acceptance specially for women. Women consider it more important than men.
6. **“Trust in in the CAV behavior”** is a priority only for women to increase acceptance. It is favorably perceived, but it is worse perceived by women. The other aspects included

in trust like “data hacking” and “detection of other road users” are not a priority neither for men nor women.

3 The Diamond Fairness Maturity Model for the tool box

Work Package 3 set out our first set of fairness characteristics for each Use Case area, this was then supplemented by the initial analysis of primary data collection and a further scoping review, as set out above, which looked to explore best practice and provide suggestions on how to improve each area of fairness to achieve a better level of maturity in the inclusiveness of the service and or employment provision. The triangulation of various types of data in the development of the maturity table.

3.1 Diamond Fairness and Inclusiveness Maturity Model

The DIAMOND project has adopted and formulated an approach to help transport organizations evaluate how fair and inclusive their services and employment conditions are based on the academic literature and the data collected from across eight European countries for the project. The DIAMOND model is based on the Safety Culture Maturity Model which was first developed in 2000 in an offshore technology report issued by the UK HSE (Fleming 2000). The model concept was developed on the basis of a five-level process issued by the Software Engineering Institute (SEI) as a mechanism to assist organizations in developing better software engineering practices (Paulk et al. 1993). The maturity model framework has been further adapted to be used in other domains and to address issues, such as project management (Fincher and Levin 1997), human resources (Helfey et al. 1995), usability (Earthy 1998) etc. The capability maturity model concept is particularly useful in the context of the DIAMOND project because it can be used as a diagnostic tool, to enable transport organisations to establish their current level of maturity and the actions required to reach the next level.

The core elements that form the safety culture maturity model have been adapted from the safety culture components listed by the UK HSE in a guidance document called HSG48 (HSE 1999). The DIAMOND maturity model is based on the characteristics identified for each Use Case on the basis of the literature review (WP3) and the initial focus groups and revised on the basis of the Fairness characteristics identified from the literature review and further revised through the datasets collected through the activities of 'Work Package 3 – Data collection' focusing on each Use Case of DIAMOND.

In summary the Fairness and inclusiveness dimensions considered are those aspects that different and diverse female users find important for a **comfortable, safe, and useful service** or for **inclusive and fair** employment in transport. In this sense they could differ from one Use Case to another as summarised above in the present document.

The key characteristics identifying different levels of maturity will be customised for each Use Case, however they fundamentally subdivide into considering fairness in employment and in usage of a transport service. This builds on WP2 (especially Deliverables D2.1 and D2.2) setting out some of the themes for D4.2 (analysing Socio-economic, demographic, and psychological choices for women in transport). It describes the identification of related specific issues (based on importance, or major research gaps, identified in the scoping review and the quantitative and

qualitative data analysis) concerning fairness for women as users of transport, and as employees in transport. This was done through a systematic-type scoping review and data analysis to provide a basis for describing and analysing a) the association between key women characteristics and transport modalities features, and b) women preferences and job characteristics of different work activities in the sector.

Figure 7: DIAMOND Fairness Maturity Model, based on Cooper M.D. (2000)

Figure 8. DIAMOND Fairness Maturity Model

3.1.1 Emerging (Level 1)

It is characteristic of processes at this level to be typically undocumented and are usually driven in an ad hoc manner by users or events. This provides an unstable or chaotic environment for the processes. Fairness is not seen as a key business risk. Most frontline staff may only use fairness as the basis for other arguments, such as changes in shift systems.

3.1.2 Managing (Level 2)

The organisation's understanding and provisions for fairness and inclusivity is average for its sector but they tend to have an initial awareness of the relevance of it, even if their performance in this sense is not being monitored. Fairness and inclusivity are seen as part of the company objectives but limited management time and effort is put into achieving them. Fairness is solely defined in terms of adherence to rules and procedures. Fairness and inclusivity are measured in terms of lagging indicators only.

3.1.3 Getting Inclusive (Level 3)

Accident rates are relatively low, but they have reached a plateau. The organisation is convinced that the involvement of the frontline employee in fairness and inclusivity is critical, if future improvements are going to be achieved. Managers recognise that a wide range of factors lead to fairness being upheld and some of these factors originate from management decisions. A significant proportion of frontline employees are willing to work with management to improve fairness and inclusivity. The performance is actively monitored and the data is used effectively.

3.1.4 Continuous Improvement (Level 4)—

The majority of staff in the organisation are convinced that fairness and inclusivity are important from both a moral and economic point of view for the service being offered and for employment conditions. Managers and frontline staff recognise that a wide range of factors are contributing to fairness being upheld and some of them come back to management decisions. Frontline staff accept personal responsibility for their own role in fairness and inclusion. The importance of all employees feeling valued and treated fairly is recognised. The organisation puts significant effort into proactive measures to improve their level of fairness and inclusivity in the services and in the organizational conditions for their employee. The performance is actively monitored using all data available.

Based on the concept of Fairness applied to the four use cases addressed by Diamond published in Hail, Y., & McQuaid, R. (2021) and taking into account all the results and learnt lessons detailed in the section 2 of this Deliverable a Fairness Maturity model has been created.

This Fairness Maturity Model (FMM) starts with a self-evaluation of the transport service provider or the employer (15 minutes effort) which provides a score about the level of fairness. Section 3 provides FMMs per each use case.

The score about the level of fairness is calculated considering some “high”, “medium” or “low” standards defined by:

- a) The interdisciplinary Diamond’s team, and
- b) External experts belonging to the WAVE association.

In these cases (a and b), these standards were collected through on-line templates:

Use Case 1: [Link](#)

Use Case 2: [Link](#)

Use Case 3: [Link](#)

Use Case-4: [Link](#)

- c) Feed-back collected from workshops (see details in section 4 of this deliverable).

After getting this score about fairness, the FMM provides some recommendations to the transport service provider or employer for managing and getting inclusion, and finally some simulations can be managed by this service provider and employer with the aim to appropriately address a continuous improvement by being aware of what points must be more priorly addressed.

All this process can be customized per different socio-demographic profiles by the transport service provider and employer.

3.2 Fairness characteristics and Maturity Models in each Use Case

for the self-evaluation framework

3.2.1 Use Case 1 Maturity Model Women as users of Public Transport

Table 9: Use Case 1 Maturity Model Women as users of Public Transport

	SCORING KEY			Score
	Poor - 1	2	Good - 3	
CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (for all users) 1) Reliability and efficiency	Service scheduled travel/transit time is always exceeded.	Good travel time for journey with some delays	Evidence of reliable transit/service operational times that allows on-time arrival at destinations	
CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (for all users) 2) Service and efficiency for commuting	Commuter isolated due to lack of service e.g. rural commuters, night, or last service options etc	Service allocation for city areas but lacking or scarce in suburban and rural zones	Good frequency and availability of service for different areas i.e. rural, urban areas irrespective of day of the week	
CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (for all users) 3) Service and efficiency access to point fo interets for all users	Lack of significant service to point of interest suited to the needs of diverse users	Good number of services allocated to some point of interest around stations vicinity and distant locations.	Level of service that allows physical access to points/facilities/service/areas within stations proximity are good for all users (e.g. including people with disabilities, parents with toddlers, elderly, carers)	
CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (for all users) 4) Integration with other modes of public transport including bus, train, etc	Poor local and inter-city mode links to many locations.	Some connection service to travel destinations	Well-connected service to communities and/or destination that suits travel purpose of users	
CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (for all users) 5) Wayfaring information	No presence of visible and/or clear real-time information available at stations and/or stops.	Operational service structure with displayed service information visible and understandable for most users but incomprehensible for some.	Presence of operative and efficient boarding system, legible and clear information for scheduled route that aids the understanding for options of transit/destination journey for all users.	

	SCORING KEY			Score
	Poor - 1	2	Good - 3	
CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (for all users) 6) Service and efficiency	Absence of substantial and dependable rail, bus, luas service allocated at all hours of the day	Frequency of operational hours of service mode fits some user travel requirements/daily travel	Reliable service modes available at all operational hours and well managed flow of waiting time to service entrée/access	
CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (for all users) 7) Service and efficiency	Trip chain travel, carers and disabled commuters have limited options to routes and stops	Some areas overserved with modal service and others lacking	Option to use different types of transport and multimodal transfer are dependable and readily available	
CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (for all users) 8) Service reliability	Waiting times are significantly longer in comparison to travel times. Presence of Inaccessible public transport transit lanes that could provide efficient flow to destination routes.	Minor sources of delay while using public transport e.g. poor transport operation and/or layout. Minimal waiting time for transit mode during travel	Selections of public transport modes and transit design allows for reliable journey travel times that suits daily travel needs of all users.	
CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (for all users) 9) Service and efficiency	Measured and inconsistent service available for leisure and work purpose.	Good quality of service for various daily interconnected travels with room for improvement	Availability of fast and consistent service between/or for single or multiple trips (chained trips) carried out through the day by women, carers etc. both for work and non-work purpose.	
CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (for all users) 10) wayfaring information and integration with other modes of public transport	Poor corresponding information on connecting modes of transport and train/service times and errors while booking on public transport platforms.	Good functioning technological system that allows for real-time travel information during journeys, adequate payment and reserve process but not understood by all users e.g. user less tech savvy	Highly efficient telematic system that allows inclusive and reliable travel and payment plan along with incorporated information throughout passenger journey.	
CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (for all users) 11) Integration with other modes of public transport including	Lack of modal option or service to usual travel destinations from the station.	Service mode appropriate for travel purpose but lacks sufficient inter-modal network connections	Location of station allows for good mode of intersection with intermodal and multiple trips suitable for travel purpose and journeys.	

	SCORING KEY			Score
	Poor - 1	2	Good - 3	
<p>CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (for all users) 12) Integration with other modes of public transport including</p>	Location of station allows for deprived interconnection, route selection and mode options for persons travelling with dependants.	Station transport network is well connected and supports convenient travel journeys for women with children, carers, and all abilities to different places	Excellent Seamless (obstacle free routes etc) and user-friendly service operations derived from station while using various modes of transit in travel journey for women with children, carers, and individuals with reduced mobility.	
<p>CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (for all users) 13) Integration with other modes of public transport including</p>	Poor integration of existing or reachable alternate to shared and on demand mobility service for last mile connections.	Proximity of accessibly service modes (public transport) are passable for all user demand but not always suitable for last mile travel.	Physical access to mode points/service within stations proximity is suitable for all users (e.g. including people with disabilities) and alternative shared mobility services for last mile connections are available (e.g. bike, scooter and car, taxis etc.)	
<p>CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (for all users) 14) Integration with other modes of public transport including</p>	Poor merge of provided modes of transport for all e.g. distanced platforms with no room for speedy/impromptu self-emergency boarding/departing of mobile vehicles, women with children or as carers.	Available interconnected modes of transport but lack accessible platforms for carers, the disabled, women with children that enables convenient boarding. e.g. self-service or service provided ramps/facility available if needed by passengers.	Incorporation of near-level platforms, level boarding and readily allocated provision/service that permits quicker passenger and/or their transit vehicles boarding and existing while using different modes public transport.	
<p>CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (for all users) 15) Design</p>	Minimal presence of well-rounded seating layout for all users.	Available public seating but few visible priorities given to parents with children, disabled, elderly etc	Good seating design that fulfils the need and/or with appropriation given to pregnant women, persons/carers with toddlers, disabled persons, elderly etc.	
<p>CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (for all users) 16) directions in stations</p>	Absence of easily navigated directions, accessible interphone communications with control-centre, present help desk attendee and clearly audible or visible service operation information.	Poorly visible vertical and horizontal signposting on platform levels. Accessible wayfinding and online planning tools evident but not user friendly for all user.	Clearly marked signage for easy wayfinding, relatable/comprehensible video, or audible announcement on travel updates for concourse and platform level suitable for all, i.e. hearing and sight disabilities.	

	SCORING KEY			Score
	Poor - 1	2	Good - 3	
CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (for all users) 17) Improved ventilation and air-conditioning	Inconducive temperature and poor ventilation in stations and on public transport	Good airing and temperature on some services (bus, trains, trams) and stations but lacking in others.	Adequate cross-ventilation and air-conditioned environments and travel modes suitable for different seasons and meet the needs of women with children, elderly etc.	
ACCESSIBILITY: (for all users) 18 Location of station	Maximum walkable access and distance to the railway station – 50% of access travels longer than 1.5 km.	Varying walking time/distance from points of interest to stations and vice versa.	Physical access to the station walkability and access. Maximum access distance to the railway station – 50% of access travels less than 1.5 km.	
ACCESSIBILITY: (for all users) 19 Location of station	Long distance (Above 400m) and unfavourable physical, symbolic, and psychological barriers that hinders or lessens the choice to walk to and from station to points of interest parents with toddlers, single parents etc.	Accessible walk commute provision from station to point of interest that suits the need of individuals with children during transit but lacking in proximity.	Within 400m convenient, pleasant safe walking conditions with good foot path conditions without dark/isolated corridors suitable for lone parents etc.	
ACCESSIBILITY: (for all users) 20 Location of station	Long distance and unfavourable walks/paths to stops/stations for connecting travels.	Accessible walks to stops/stations during transit for all users.	Less/fewer walk distance/times between locations while carrying out single or multiple trips for women with children, carers, disabled etc.	
ACCESSIBILITY: (for all users) 21 Reliability and efficiency	Unreliable service, low frequency, inefficient connections between transport modes and services, lack of feeder public transport, bike and car sharing services. Without alignment to the needs of minority passenger segments.	Reliable service, high frequency, good integration with other modes of transport. Induction loops, fixed ramps, help points, handrails, mobile customer assistance points.	Efficient and accessible multimodal transfers, integrating ticketing systems, presence of feeder public transport, presence of bike sharing and car sharing service. Services are in line with the need of minority segments of passengers.	

	SCORING KEY			Score
	Poor - 1	2	Good - 3	
SAFETY AND SECURITY: (for all users) 22) harassment and pickpocketing	Presence of complaint information points, but mostly lack surveillance personnel when cases needed.	Presence of complaint information point but security or transport personnel sometimes lacking a gender sensitive approach to users of service but not available for all service.	Proportioned and readily available complaint information points on transit mode or at station/stops for single travellers, women with children etc available at urban, rural or sub-urban areas in the case of safety violation and presence security measures and accessible security staffs.	
SAFETY AND SECURITY: (for all users) 23) harassment and pickpocketing	Facilities and trains are not equipped with modern tools for monitoring/reporting of violence	Available platforms and information on personal safety violation with slow response/follow up.	Easy to understand platforms and information on the process to report cases of personal safety violations openly or privately.	
SAFETY AND SECURITY: (for all users) 24) harassment and pickpocketing	Poor lighting for the close areas of the station.	Surrounding of station equipped with visible but poor lighting in some areas.	High visibility and improved lighting for the surrounding area of the station.	
SAFETY AND SECURITY: (for all users) 25) harassment and pickpocketing	Stations surrounding layout prohibits visibility of amenities and approaching service or modes that fits all users	Forthcoming modes of travel are impartially visible and appropriate for most users nonetheless lacking in some locations.	Clear visibility of approaching and departing vehicles, amenities, and safety guidelines present/suitable regardless of living environment, gender, responsibilities (parent or carer), age or disability.	
SAFETY AND SECURITY: (for all users) 26) Design	Station design allows poor/closed environments that are not within view sub-areas or persons	Some occluded areas in station surroundings but passengers within view of other passenger and staff	Good environment visibility and open areas within view of other area, other passengers, staff, and security personnel.	
SAFETY AND SECURITY: (for all users) 27) Harassment and pickpocketing	Entrance and exist not within sight or easily located by all users	Station surrounding directions not effectively linked to entrance and exit but within view	All entrances and exit are within view with directions of surroundings well marked and obvious	

	SCORING KEY			Score
	Poor - 1	2	Good - 3	
SAFETY AND SECURITY: (for all users) 28) Harassment and pickpocketing	No obvious or clearly marked automated or natural surveillance and security points at the surrounding areas of the station	Some station surveillance visible and absent in some areas	Presence of visible CCTV, security aids (Police/transport staff), automated platforms (Emergency alarms, panic buttons, phone, strips) clearly visible in the vicinity around station.	
SAFETY AND SECURITY: (for all users) 29) Display advertisements for public awareness campaigns and for publicizing helpline numbers	No visible display advertisements for public awareness campaigns and for publicizing helpline numbers.	Presence of helpline number but no clearly publicised guidelines or advertisements or movements for public awareness campaigns	Evidence of well-informed advertised public awareness movements along with information and/or helpline contacts.	
SAFETY AND SECURITY: (for all users) 30) Overcrowding and emergency management	Poor allocation, structure, or design that does not give room for personal space or crowd control.	Public transport allows for personal space while travelling but low allocation for multiple users e.g. mothers with children, disabled, careers etc when needed.	Redesigned space within the trains that allows adequate personal space, conducive travel experience and the regulation of crowds for users of public transport whom are mothers with children, elderly, careers, disabled etc.	
SAFETY AND SECURITY: (for all users) 31) Overcrowding and emergency management	Stations and trains are not empowered with hardware and software measures for handling overcrowding.	Supporting tariff measures for reducing the overcrowding (shifting the flows out of the peak hours).	System for real-time train crowding information provision - Apps and websites highlighting less crowded carriages; Advanced solutions for platform overcrowding (wide and long platform area, improved design of tunnels, enough number of stairs, enough check-in and check-out posts), crowd controller system.	
SAFETY AND SECURITY: (for all users) 32) Overcrowding and emergency management	Traditional emergency management without advanced procedures and tools for acting in case of emergency	Developed emergency plan with several emergency call points; Clear emergency procedures; Passenger information and security systems.	Emergency call points established and for passengers available (on a number of points) emergency procedures in trains and at stations with detailed evacuation plans; enough number of emergency exits for evacuation.	

	SCORING KEY			Score
	Poor - 1	2	Good - 3	
SAFETY AND SECURITY: (for all users) 33) Overcrowding and emergency management	Cramped and insecure stop/station/transit links/locations while travelling.	Good universal design in stop/station/transit that allows a decent flow for carers, women with children, elderly and with disabilities.	Access to well-structured and safer transit network for better travel experience e.g. public space (congestion avoided etc), walk pathways (road crossings etc), stops and station.	
SAFETY AND SECURITY: (for all users) 34) Overcrowding and emergency management	Available seat without standard that accommodate the disabled, carers, women with children.	Seating outline gives options for more/less social interactions with some room for efficient exits for women with children, carers etc.	Improved seating layout that accommodates emergency exits for all users and with less dealings with other public transport users if needed.	
			Raw Score I - (34*3)	
			Divide by 34	

3.2.2 Use Case II Maturity Model Women as Users of Autonomous vehicles

Table 10: Use Case II Maturity Model Women as Users of Autonomous vehicles

Diamond Fairness Maturity Model Self Evaluation audit: Autonomous Vehicles				
	SCORING KEY			Score
	Poor - 1	2	Good - 3	
CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (for all passengers) 1) Multi-tasking Automated driving confidence and disengagement.	Guidelines: When the level of confidence and trust in the AVs increases is easier for the "drivers" to perform non-driving related tasks as they feel comfortable disengaging themselves from the driving issues. Self-assessment question: How do you evaluate the degree of disengaging from driving issues to allow non-driving related tasks (NDRT) ?			
		Poor - 1 "Drivers" do not fully disengage from the driving tasks and do not feel confident when conducting other tasks while the AV keeps control.	2 "Drivers" may disengage from the driving tasks with a minimum supervision and feel confident when conducting other tasks while the AV keeps control.	Good - 3 "Drivers" feel confident when conducting other tasks and specific automated functions are incorporated for this purpose such as strategies to avoid motion sickness, adaptation of the driving mode for different NDRT...

<p>CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (for all passengers)</p> <p>2) Multi-tasking Interaction between passengers.</p>	<p>Guidelines: Interior layout and seating design solutions should provide different configurations to allow different degrees of interaction between passengers, from a more private or individual space to a more common space to promote the interaction between passengers, including caring tasks (e.g. children).</p> <p>Self-assessment question: How do you evaluate the features incorporated in the AVs to modulate and facilitate the degree of interaction with other passengers?</p>			
	<p>Poor - 1</p>	<p>2</p>	<p>Good - 3</p>	
	<p>No specific features are incorporated to facilitate the degree of desired interaction.</p>	<p>Limited features have been incorporated to facilitate interaction between passenger or individual privacy.</p>	<p>The interior layout and seating solution provides the possibility of different configurations addressing the desired degree of interaction with other passengers, from a set of private and individual spaces to a common space to facilitate interaction and care of other passengers.</p>	
<p>CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (for all passengers)</p> <p>3) Multi-tasking Comfort in Non-Driving Related Tasks (NDRT).</p>	<p>Guidelines: Simultaneous / Non-Diving Related Task must be performed comfortably by passengers/drivers. For this purpose, interior and ambient comfort facilities must be designed according with the identified tasks needs.</p> <p>Self-assessment question: How do you evaluate the degree of automated vehicle facilitates to perform a non-driving related task (NDRT)?</p>			
	<p>Poor - 1</p>	<p>2</p>	<p>Good - 3</p>	
	<p>Basic specific designs are incorporated to facilitate performing other tasks while AV takes control. (e.g. plugs for nomadic devices)</p>	<p>Limited features have been incorporated to facilitate the simultaneous activities. (e.g. Adaptation of the illumination and auxiliary surfaces)</p>	<p>Specific features are incorporated and interior layout is easily reconfigurable for different task and postures (e.g. Adaptable sitting and auxiliary surfaces, ambient comfort adaptable to the task, electronic facilities for working or entertainment...)</p>	
<p>CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (for all passengers)</p> <p>4) Travel time Trip-Chaining</p>	<p>Guidelines: Considering travel time from a gender perspective implies considering the different mobility patterns, one specific characteristic of women displacement is the connection of different displacements more complex than men (e.g. dropping the kids in the school before going to the work).</p> <p>Self-assessment question: How do you evaluate the features incorporated in the AVs to save time to destination and facilitate trip chaining (chained displacements)?</p>			
	<p>Poor - 1</p>	<p>2</p>	<p>Good - 3</p>	

	<p>Drivers do not believe AV's improves travel times compared with conventional cars. AVs offer information and control of features (estimated time to destination point (GPS) and suggest shortest path to destination considering different variables such as traffic status).</p>	<p>AVs offer options (driving mode, green wave options...) to improve travel time in case of need.</p>	<p>AVs offers automated driving function and not driving functions focused on chained displacements (e.g. car parking or waiting functions, planning complete route and task -list...)</p>	
<p>CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (for all passengers)</p> <p>5) Social Benefits Ecological sustainability, other road users impact and traffic flow.</p>	<p>Guidelines: A driving behavior with low ecologic impact, respectful with other road users and contributing to the improvement of traffic flow is beneficial to the community.</p> <p>Self-assessment question: How do you evaluate the communication and control of social benefits of the AV by HMI?</p>			
	Poor - 1	2	Good - 3	
	<p>Limited social benefits are communicated by HMI to occupants or not properly perceived (ecological impact).</p>	<p>Social benefits are communicated and perceived by occupants with proper indicators (ecological impact +).</p>	<p>Occupants are informed continuously by the system on social benefits allowing them to take informed decisions when selecting the automatic driving parameters (info for decision making). (e.g. by selecting this driving mode your car reduces 30% of energy consumption and it is a 10% more the respectful with pedestrians)</p>	
<p>ACCESSIBLE (for all passengers)</p> <p>6) Extremely flexible concept to adapt to the different users' needs.</p>	<p>Guidelines: Some studies see the development of the AVs and their use to the development of a Sharing Service, that would imply a new concept of using the car with nomad passengers.</p> <p>Self-assessment question: How do you evaluate the flexibility of AV considering that "The user of the car is a nomad traveler with their own luggage"?</p>			
	Poor - 1	2	Good - 3	

	Car interior is not flexible or has not any adaptation features for passengers and luggage.	Limited flexibility interior features for passengers and luggage.	Flexible interior (e.g. different support spaces/surfaces allowing different configurations, open spaces fewer specific gadgets, flat surfaces, free from corners and bumps and easy to put and secure the luggage, and belongings and easy to clean).	
ACCESSIBLE (for all passengers) 7) Vehicle shape (children friendly)	<p>Guidelines: The mobility of care, mainly performed by women, implies the displacement with children.</p> <p>Self-assessment question: How do you evaluate the degree the AVs design in children friendly?</p>			
	Poor - 1	2	Good - 3	
	Design is not children friendly.	Limited children adaptation and/or only focused on safety aspect. Seating security for children (from babies to teenagers). The AV incorporates seats that may transform into busters for some sizes.	Children friendly design. Design has considered children as a passenger and need (i.e. Design of the space to be comfortable for children behaviour and for the carer of the children for caring, monitoring and interacting with children).	
ACCESSIBLE (for all passengers) 8) Women Ergonomics in design	<p>Guidelines: Women and men are different considering physical and physiological characteristics.</p> <p>Self-assessment question: How do you evaluate the degree of adaptation to women specific physical and physiological characteristics?</p>			
	Poor - 1	2	Good - 3	
	Limited application of women ergonomics in design such as anthropometrics, reaches, forces.	Women ergonomics applied in design such as anthropometrics, reaches, forces and consider women variability and pregnancy	Women ergonomics applied and further anatomical and physiological differences between women and men such as temperature perception (for thermal comfort), voice pitch (for HMI), typical postures (for interior layout), proprioceptors (vehicle dynamics) and systems works as fully for women as they do for men.	

<p>ACCESSIBLE (for all passengers)</p> <p>9) Gender and intersectional factors in design</p>	<p>Guidelines: In addition to the physical and physiological differences we need to consider gender factors for a fair design.</p> <p>Self-assessment question: How do you evaluate the degree of the design is fair with gender and adapted to women needs?</p>			
	Poor - 1	2	Good - 3	
	<p>The design has not considered the risk of stereotyping or reinforce existing social roles.</p>	<p>Gender differences has been explored to study different patterns of use for defining product users' needs and in design solutions and AV HMI provides a Gender-Neutral Conversation.</p>	<p>Gender and other related intersectional variables have been identified and considered to establish a proper user centered design process and validation ensuring any disadvantage in the identified groups.</p>	
<p>ACCESSIBLE (for all passengers)</p> <p>10) Inclusive design</p>	<p>Guidelines: The users of the AV are a varied group, with different needs and requirements.</p> <p>Self-assessment question: How do you evaluate the degree of the design consider the variability in the population needs?</p>			
	Poor - 1	2	Good - 3	
	<p>Design has not considered variability in population and it has a high risk of excluding groups such as elderly people.</p>	<p>Design has followed principles of design for all.</p>	<p>Specific feature to facilitate by the use population with special needs including certain type of functional diversity.</p>	
<p>SAFETY AND SECURITY (for all passengers)</p> <p>11) Ergonomics/ Biomechanics in safety</p>	<p>Guidelines: Traditionally, with few exceptions, the car industry has only considered male models for designing the safety systems of the car.</p> <p>Self-assessment question: How do you evaluate the degree of the safety are fair with women?</p>			
	Poor - 1	2	Good - 3	
	<p>AVs safety is designed without considering basic anatomical and physiological differences between men and women (different breast sizes, ...). Safety standards based on mainly in men population</p>	<p>AVs safety is designed considering other differences between men and women (e.g. voice pitch, vision field). Safety standards including women and all sizes.</p>	<p>Safety standards based on women fair data bases and including all sizes, pregnancy. AVs safety is designed considering different uses and environments (e.g. trip chaining, mobility of care) and further physiological differences such us driving styles, reaction times, preferences,</p>	

			stress and workload levels.	
SAFETY AND SECURITY (for all passengers) 12) Communication to generate trust	Guidelines: An appropriate communication between the AVs and the passengers or drivers may impact highly in the trust and satisfaction of the whole system. Self-assessment question: How do you evaluate the degree of the AV communication with the "driver" is adapted to the user and context?			
	Poor - 1	2	Good - 3	
	No possibility to adapt the quantity or complexity of information neither to "driver" or simultaneous task.	"Drivers" configure the amount of amount and complexity information according to the situation or their characteristics.	Automatic adaptation to the amount and complexity of information according to the experience, preference, task, trust, context to not overwhelm "driver" and evolve over the time according to trust improvement and experience gained using the vehicle.	
SAFETY AND SECURITY (for all passengers) 13) Safe ergonomics	Guidelines: The previous experience of the drivers with advanced control systems, or their preferences (e.g. like to have everything under control) conditionate the preferences for the interaction with the AVs concerning the control issues. Self-assessment question: How do you evaluate the degree of the AV "driver" control and supervision is adapted to the user and context?			
	Poor - 1	2	Good - 3	
	No possibility to adapt the control and supervision level neither to "driver" or situation.	"Drivers" configure the control and supervision level according to the situation (context) or their characteristics.	Automatic adaptation control and supervision level according to the experience, preference, task, trust, context and evolve over the time according to trust improvement and experience gained using the vehicle.	

Diamond Fairness Maturity Model Self Evaluation audit: Autonomous Vehicles				
	<i>Score 1</i>	<i>Score 2</i>	<i>Score 3</i>	

SCORING KEY				
	Poor		Good	SCORE
CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (of drivers) Multi-Tasking	Basic specific designs incorporated include ability to undertake other tasks while AV takes control Drivers do not have confidence in conducting other tasks while the AV is in control	Specific features have been incorporated to facilitate multi-tasking i.e. related with work and communication (laptop, detachable table...) for all passengers.	Specific features related to motion sickness and care mobility or trip-chaining have been incorporated to facilitate multi-tasking (access to children...) Training is provided to include a focus on how to take over control if needed	Please provide examples of current situation
CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (of drivers) Travel time	Drivers do not believe AV's increase travel times and reduce congestion	AVs offers options (driving behaviour, green wave options...) to improve travel in case of need.	Special features thought for trip chaining (e.g. intelligent waiting/parking when dropping children at school) AVs offer an estimated time to destination point (GPS) and suggests shortest path to destination considering different variables such as traffic status.	
CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (of drivers) Vehicle behaviour	Little control of vehicle dynamic variables.	More than one feature may be personalised (e.g. preferred sportive/comfort driving, eco-efficient/fastest driving...)	More than one feature may be personalised (e.g. preferred sportive/comfort driving, eco-efficient/fastest driving, motion sickness minimization)	
ACCESSIBLE (for all drivers) Vehicle shape (getting in and out of the car)	No specific or very basic measures or features design to facilitate getting in and out of the car.	Limited specific features for getting in and out of the car for specific groups (elderly, children, pregnant women, ...)	Direct access of a wheelchair to the car and trolleys.	
ACCESSIBLE (for all drivers) Vehicle shape (seating)	No specific measures to facilitate seating of children or people with special needs.	Basic specific feature to facilitate seating of children or people with special needs (e.g. booster seat incorporated in standard seat).	Specific feature to facilitate seating for children, pregnant women or people with special needs (e.g. seating partially swivelling or tilting to facilitate incorporation of elderly persons).	

ACCESSIBILITY (for all drivers) Vehicle shape (shopping/suitcases)	No specific measures or features design to facilitate loading and unloading the car.	Basic specific features to facilitate loading or unloading the car.	Specific features to facilitate loading and unloading the car, personalize interior to increase the boot of the car.	
ACCESSIBILITY (for all drivers) Human Machine Interface (ergonomics)	There are no measures in place to support physical aspects such as variations in height, range of motion, vision and hearing deficits are not	There are limited provisions –	AI is cognisant of supporting accessibility in relation to people with functional diversity, Vision difficulties. Physical difficulties. Hard of hearing. Specific cognitive situations. And the ability to recognise and differentiate between female and male voices	
ACCESSIBILITY (for all drivers) Human Machine Interface (warning and communication system)	There are no specific measures for warning and communication systems	Information systems (voice + pictures. Physical commands + voice) do not work as fully for women as they do for men.	All warning systems and internal communications are suitable for use by owners with both vision and hearing impairments	
SAFETY AND SECURITY (for all users) Trust in technology	Trust levels in technology are low – particularly with women	Trust varies across only certain technological solutions, i.e. Drivers have no trust in using AV's in inclement weather conditions	The trust in technology is under any circumstance of weather, high traffic flow, failure circumstances, and speed.	

SAFETY AND SECURITY (for all users) Human Errors - Specific training for AV drivers	There is no affordable AV training available for new owners	The training available for new AV owners is limited and costly	Regular and affordable training for all new owners of AV's is available locally	
SAFETY AND SECURITY (for all users) Safe ergonomics	AVs safety is designed without considering basic anatomical and physiological differences between men and women (different breast sizes, ...).	AVs safety is designed considering other differences between men and women (e.g. voice pitch, vision field).	AVs safety is designed taking into account different uses and environments (e.g. trip chaining, mobility of care)	

3.2.3 Use Case III Maturity Model Women as users: Bike Sharing

Table 11: Use Case III Maturity Model Women as users: Bike Sharing

Diamond Fairness Maturity Model Self Evaluation audit: Bike Sharing					
	Score 1	Score 2	Score 3		
	SCORING KEY			Score	
	Poor		Good		
CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (for all users) Suitable bikes for those traveling with children, carrying packages and shopping	Available bikes are not suited to riders travelling with children or travelling for shopping	Measures have been identified to provide accessories to facilitate traveling with children or shopping – not yet implemented	Ability to access a bike with child seat or basket for traveling with children or shopping		Please provide examples of current situation
CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (for all users) Promote cycling as a legitimate form of	No campaigns to promote cycling as a legitimate form of transportation for people of BAME background	Measures identified to sensitise individuals of BAME background on	At least 4 sensitisation campaigns targeted at BAME groups in a year		

Diamond Fairness Maturity Model Self Evaluation audit: Bike Sharing					
	Score 1	Score 2	Score 3		
	SCORING KEY			Score	
	Poor		Good		
transportation in BAME communities		cycling but not implemented			
CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (for all users) Bikes suited to local topography and weather conditions	No plans to ensure the bikes and accessories are suitable for the local terrain and weather	No plans identified to equip stations with bikes and accessories suitable for the local terrain and weather but not implemented	Implementation of plans ensure stations are equip with bikes and accessories suitable for the local terrain and weather		
CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (for all users) available to those in low-income neighbourhoods etc.	There are no facilities available in low-income communities	Measures identified to site stations in low-income communities but not implemented	Implementation of plans to establish stations in low-income communities Ability to access a bike within 400m radius in these communities		
ACCESSIBILITY: (for all users) Location of docking stations - proximity and convenience	No docking stations in local residential neighbourhoods	Measures identified to site docking stations in residential neighbourhoods – although not fully	Implementation of plans to establish docking stations in residential neighbourhoods		

Diamond Fairness Maturity Model Self Evaluation audit: Bike Sharing					
	Score 1	Score 2	Score 3		
	SCORING KEY			Score	
	Poor		Good		
(rural/urban and low-income communities)		implemented as yet	Ability to access a bike within 400m radius of residential neighbourhoods		
ACCESSIBILITY: (for all users) Costs including membership fees	Absence of subsidise rates of cycle hire for low-income users (unemployed or students etc.)	Measures identified to subsidise low-income users but not yet implemented	Concessions and reduced costs for unemployed or students etc.		
ACCESSIBILITY: (for all users) Service reliability	Limited availability of bikes at all stations	Plans identified to ensure system reliability (bikes availability at all stations) but not implemented	System implemented to ensure station always have bikes available for rental. At least 80% of stations always have bikes available for rentals Variety of bikes available including e-bikes		

Diamond Fairness Maturity Model Self Evaluation audit: Bike Sharing					
	Score 1	Score 2	Score 3		
	SCORING KEY			Score	
	Poor		Good		
ACCESSIBILITY: (for all users) Public awareness of scheme	Limited knowledge of facility at a local level	Occasional public awareness campaigns (1 or 2 in a year)	Regular public awareness campaigns (At least 4 in a year) High uptake of facility		
ACCESSIBILITY: (for all users) Simple and flexible signing-up process	Existing sign-up processes based on memberships via internet or smartphones unchanged -	Plans advanced to implement internet and smartphone free signing-up process or membership	Ability to sign-up for membership without the internet, smartphone, or credit card		
ACCESSIBILITY: (for all users) Payment option	Absence of measures to make cash payment (Inability to hire bike and pay by cash)	Measures identified but not implemented to offer cash payment membership	Both Credit card payment and cash payment options available (Ability to hire bike and pay by cash)		
ACCESSIBILITY: (for all users) Sheltered docking stations	Docking stations lack any form of shelter from weather conditions No changing facilities are available for riders to change clothes	Some measures in place to provide shelter and changing facilities for docking stations	Significant implementation of measures to provide shelter for docking stations (At least --% of docking stations are sheltered)		

Diamond Fairness Maturity Model Self Evaluation audit: Bike Sharing					
	Score 1	Score 2	Score 3		
	SCORING KEY			Score	
	Poor		Good		
SAFETY AND SECURITY: (for all users) Presence of CCTV systems to improve user perception of security	There are no security measures at docking stations (e.g. no CCTV systems)	Plans in place to ensure stations are equip with CCTV systems but not yet implemented	At least > 80% of docking stations have CCTV cameras		
SAFETY AND SECURITY: (for all users) Separate biking infrastructure	Existing infrastructure does not include car free lanes specifically for cyclists	Limited access to separate cycle lanes free from vehicular traffic	Significant Implementation of measures to separate cyclist from vehicular traffic have been put in place		
SAFETY AND SECURITY: (for all users) Personal safety – maintenance of bikes	Less than 50% of bikes meet safety and maintenance requirements i.e. well-functioning safety lights and brakes etc.	On average 50% to 70% of bikes have well-functioning safety lights and brakes	At least 80% of bikes have well-functioning safety lights and brakes		
SAFETY AND SECURITY: (for all users) Safety equipment provided including helmets, hi-vis vest, ponchos	Users' inability to access safety helmets, hi-vis vests or rain poncho when hiring a bike	Measures identified to equip stations with safety equipment but not yet implemented	All docking stations have the facility to provide safety equipment such as cycle helmets, his-vis-vests and rain ponchos etc.		

Diamond Fairness Maturity Model Self Evaluation audit: Bike Sharing					
	Score 1	Score 2	Score 3		
	SCORING KEY			Score	
	Poor		Good		
SAFETY AND SECURITY: (for all users) Ease of reporting problems/complaints about bike-sharing facilities	No measures to enhance and simplify user complaint and feedback channels	Plans advanced well to promote and facilitates user complaint and feedback systems	Simplified and inclusive complaint management systems implemented to facilitate reporting		

3.2.4 Use Case IV Maturity Model Women as employees in the Transport Sector

Table 12: Use Case IV Maturity Model Women as employees in the Transport Sector

Diamond Fairness Maturity Model Self Evaluation audit: Women Employees					
	Score 1	Score 2	Score 3		
	SCORING KEY			Score	
	Poor		Good		
<p>CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (for all employees)</p> <p>Promotion and development opportunities</p>	There is no support for employees returning to work after a leave of absence	There is an awareness, but no policy implemented as yet	Employees returning from leave of absence (maternity, paternity etc.) have equal access to promotion, training, and development opportunities		Please provide examples of current situation
<p>CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (for all employees)</p> <p>Promotion and development opportunities</p>	Limited training opportunities specifically for women	An awareness of training requirements not yet fully met	Equal access for all employees to training and development opportunities regardless of gender, age, ability etc.		
<p>CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (for all employees)</p> <p>Promotion and development opportunities</p>	Limited promotion opportunities available for women	Attempts have been made to promote women internally	There is an internal policy focused on promoting women specifically internally		
<p>CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (for all employees)</p> <p>family friendly</p>	There are no opportunities for flexible shift/working patterns	Flexible working is not currently available but something the	There are opportunities for all staff to access flexible working patterns (dependent on their role)		

Diamond Fairness Maturity Model Self Evaluation audit: Women Employees					
	Score 1	Score 2	Score 3		
	SCORING KEY			Score	
	Poor		Good		
working conditions		organisations is considering			
CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (for all employees) family friendly working conditions	There is no support for or ability to work remotely or home working	This organisation is unable to provide flexible opportunities due to its business There are limited roles that can be done remotely or working from home	All staff have the opportunity for remote/home and flexible working to suit caring responsibilities		
CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (for all employees) family friendly working conditions	There are no parttime/job share roles in this organisation No ability to provide part-time employment	Aware of the need for part time/job share but no official company policy	Flexible Working Hours and part time arrangements are encouraged and lead to excellent progression paths.		

Diamond Fairness Maturity Model Self Evaluation audit: Women Employees					
	Score 1	Score 2	Score 3		
	SCORING KEY			Score	
	Poor		Good		
<p>CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (for all employees)</p> <p>Training, work environment & Culture</p>	<p>There is a general lack of female role models across the organisation, particularly in management.</p>	<p>There are a few role models for women but not across all of the organisation</p>	<p>A collegiate work environment is encouraged across the business and supported by visible role models</p> <p>Processes in place to support safety of employees reporting bullying or harassment from either colleagues/management</p> <p>Mentoring and role models (for women)</p>		
<p>CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (for all employees)</p> <p>Training, work environment & Culture</p>	<p>The organisation does not provide any training with regards to diversity or unconscious bias.</p>	<p>The company attempts to encourage a culture of diversity and gender equality as the accepted norm. No consistency to delivery</p>	<p>The company insists on and promotes diversity and gender equality as the accepted norm and has a formal complaints protocol in place.</p>		
<p>CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (for all employees)</p>	<p>There is a disparity in salary between men and women in the organisation</p>	<p>Work is in progress to increase parity between male and female employees but</p>	<p>All employees have access to equal pay and equal working terms and conditions</p>		

Diamond Fairness Maturity Model Self Evaluation audit: Women Employees					
	Score 1	Score 2	Score 3		
	SCORING KEY			Score	
	Poor		Good		
Salary and conditions		not yet completed			
CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (for all employees) Salary and conditions	The majority of current female employees are fixed term short contracts	Work is in progress to increase parity between male and female employees but not yet completed	Full time permanent contracts		
CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS (for all employees) Salary and conditions	Employees on zero hours contracts	Working on removing current zero hours contracts	There are no zero hours contract employees in this organisation		
ACCESSIBILITY (for all potential employees) Recruitment of women	No specific focus on gender in recruitment policies Jobs and roles identified by gender only	HR policies encourage gender balance in some roles but not all	Gender Neutral recruitment policies are in place for all roles Female employees are encouraged to apply for non-traditional roles in the organisation i.e. train drivers/mechanics		

Diamond Fairness Maturity Model Self Evaluation audit: Women Employees					
	Score 1	Score 2	Score 3		
	SCORING KEY			Score	
	Poor		Good		
	Ethnicity and caring responsibilities are not considered when recruitment takes place				
ACCESSIBILITY: (for all potential employees) Specific training and career development for women	Access to training or upskilling is only available when required and suited to the organisations needs with limited scope for progression	Employees are encouraged to upskill, reskill, retrain at their own expense	Equal access for women to training opportunities for general upskilling and transferring roles (e.g. administrative role to technical role)		
ACCESSIBILITY: (for all potential employees) Specific training and career development for women	There is no women only training provision	Most training provision offered is focused on men and traditional male roles	Financial support provided for training and academic study to support employment roles Availability of women only training courses for progression and promotion Equal access for younger and older women to progress within the organisation		
ACCESSIBILITY: (for all potential employees)	There are no women only facilities available	Women employees are currently using	Provision of separate toilets, changing and shower facilities for women		

Diamond Fairness Maturity Model Self Evaluation audit: Women Employees					
	Score 1	Score 2	Score 3		
	SCORING KEY			Score	
	Poor		Good		
Design		disabled facilities			
ACCESSIBILITY: (for all potential employees) Design	There is no attention paid to internal ergonomics for employees e.g. seat size and comfort for drivers of all sexes	Provision is available if you are aware of who to contact	Suitable ergonomics for employees in roles e.g. seat size and comfort for drivers of all sexes Incorporation of design to facilitate emergency evacuation for employees of all physical abilities/disabilities		
ACCESSIBILITY: (for all potential employees) Design	There are no specific arrangements in place for employees with chronic illness/disabilities e.g. reduced hearing/sight issues (e.g. widening doors for wheelchair access, adaptive software for employees with hearing or sight loss)	Consideration is given to some mobility issues but not all	Work environment is suitable for all employees with chronic illness/disabilities e.g. reduced hearing/sight issues (e.g. widening doors for wheelchair access, adaptive software for employees with hearing or sight loss)		
SAFETY AND SECURITY: (for all frontline employees)	There are no formal internal processes to allow employees to report concerns	The processes in place to report safety concerns are done in an adhoc way	Open and accessible processes in place for reporting safety/security issues by employees		

Diamond Fairness Maturity Model Self Evaluation audit: Women Employees					
	Score 1	Score 2	Score 3		
	SCORING KEY			Score	
	Poor		Good		
HR Policies gender awareness and anti-bullying		with no formal structure			
SAFETY AND SECURITY: (for all frontline employees) HR Policies gender awareness and anti-bullying	If concerns are reported there is no mechanism available for management to feedback to employees	The processes in place to report safety concerns are done in an adhoc way with no formal structure	Open and accessible processes in place for reporting and responding to employee's reporting physical stress/psychological stress/both		
SAFETY AND SECURITY: (for all frontline employees) Personal Protection Equipment suitable for women	All workwear and uniforms are of universal design – for men and women	Some workwear and PPE is of a universal design with some gender specific PPE available	Suitable and appropriate PPE for all sexes is provided to all employees Workwear and uniforms are designed to suit women		

4 Workshop organised and feedback received.

Following the design thinking sessions, the work for task 5.1 has continued with an analysis of the outcomes of these sessions, to refine customer journey mapping, understand what functionalities would be offered by the toolbox, and its presentation in an initial mock-up for the main functionalities of the toolbox (in this deliverable, we omit the mock-up of minor functionalities, such as password recovery, to facilitate the readability of the document).

4.1 Use case IV revision workshop: 14th of December 2020

The topics that were discussed at this workshop included:

1. Exploring the challenges faced and good practices found in transport organisations surrounding appropriate considerations for women as users
2. The development of a benchmarking or maturity model for fairness in the use of different surface transport services
3. A workshop discussion to summarise key areas of future work and data collection.

4.1.1 Workshop Agenda

The agenda for the Use Case IV revision workshop in December 2020 is reported in ANNEX I.

4.1.2 Overview of expert invited

The workshop was attended by over 35 experts on transport from the United Kingdom, Ireland, Colombia, France, Romania, Belgium, Austria, Spain, Italy and Poland ranging from Business Managers/Developers, Policy Advisers, Project Officers, Engineering Directors, Researchers and Transport Specialists, among others.

The list below present the invited speakers that presented during the workshop alongside the Diamond researchers:

Cristina Marolda - Former Policy Officer, Chair of the advisory board for the Diamond project

Cristina Marolda has been for almost 30 years Policy Officer at the European Commission, in charge of Research & Innovation in the transport system. She has always been active in supporting focused research and policy mainstreaming to reach a proper gender balance in mobility. She is now an independent expert on Inclusive Transport Systems and Governance of Innovation and Disruptive Technologies.

Wei-Shiuen Ng - Advisor Sustainable Transport and Global Outreach, International Transport Forum, OECD

Wei-Shiuen Ng is Advisor on Sustainable Transport and Global Outreach in the International Transport Forum (ITF) at the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). She leads gender in transport related research and policy analysis at the ITF, as well as transport and climate change policy development. Wei-Shiuen is also an Adjunct Professor at the Paris Institute of Political Science (Sciences Po), member of the Scientific Committee of the World Conference on Transport Research Society (WCTRS) and co-chairs the Special Interest Group on Transport and Climate Change. She currently serves on the United States Transportation

Research Board (TRB) of the National Academics Committee on Transportation in the Developing Countries and Committee on Transportation Demand management.

Lorna Gibson - Training Director, QTS Group

Lorna Gibson is Training Director for the QTS Group, a large enterprise owned by Renew Holdings and supplying Railway Infrastructure Engineering services throughout the United Kingdom. Lorna's key role within the Group is that of managing Director of QTS Training Ltd, a subsidiary company which supplies railway safety, on-track plant, health and safety and construction management training to the rail and wider industries. Lorna is also a Director, and Past president, of the Ayrshire Chamber of commerce and Industry, sits on the Developing Young Workforce Ayrshire Steering Group and is Vice Chair of the Hansel Foundation.

Linda Allen - Talent Manager, Irish Rail

Experienced Talent Manager with a demonstrated history of working in the transportation/trucking/railroad industry. Skilled in coaching, Training Programme Design, Training Delivery, Management, Leadership, Interviewing and Personality Testing. Strong human resources professional with a Master's degree focused in Work and Organisational Psychology from Dublin City University.

Charlene Wallace - Director Network rail, Women in Rail

Charlene brings over 20 years' experience in the public transport sector having previously held senior board director roles in rail and aviation, including most recently with Virgin Trains. She has a strong track record of delivering and leading customer-focused transformation in transport and has a wide range of transition and business change experience including – improving customer and stakeholder processes and communications, delivering customer initiatives, employee engagement and organisational change.

Charlene's focus at Network Rail will be with our customers and passengers. She will be leading the National Passenger and Customer Experience team (NP&Cx), which includes the national stations team, and the new Passenger Information During Disruption (PIDD) team. She is also the interim Director for Freight, representing the interests of the rail freight industry across the UK.

Heather Waugh - Train Driver, Women in Rail

Heather Waugh joined the railway as a Train Driver with Scotrail in August 2006, having previously been an Operational Manager with Royal Mail for 10 years. In January 2019 Heather became Freightliner's first ever female train driver in Scotland and, indeed, the only female freight train driver at all in Scotland.

She is passionate about issues around mental health, equality, diversity and inclusion and believes strongly in breaking down barriers, both mental and physical, which prevent women from excelling in areas that are still heavily male dominated within the rail industry. She won 'Highly Commended' at the Women in Rail Awards 2020 in the category of 'Inspirational Woman of the Year'.

The following experts represented the Diamond team

Yvonne Hail - Research Fellow, University of Stirling

Dr Yvonne Hail is a research fellow at the University of Stirling. Yvonne is a former transport manager who worked in the construction industry in Scotland who is now qualitative researcher with experience in conducting international and interdisciplinary research projects.

Maria Chiara Leva - Lecturer, Technological University Dublin

M. Chiara Leva is a Lecturer in Technological University Dublin in the College of Environmental Health, she is an associated PI in the Science and Technology in Advanced Manufacturing research centre and in the Centre for Innovative Human systems both in Trinity College Dublin. Chiara is the co-chair of technical committee on Human Reliability for the European Safety and Reliability Association, former chair of the Irish Ergonomics Society and co-chair of the scientific steering group for the first Symposium on Human Mental Workload (H-Workload). Dr Leva has more than 70 publications on Human Factors, Operational Risk Assessment and Safety Management in Science and engineering Journals, she is a member of the editorial board for two of those journals.

4.1.3 Overview of feedback sessions organised

The questions asked during this feedback session included:

Use case IV Poll questions:

How would YOU define fairness in the context of "fair employment for women in the transport sector" **open text box**.

1. In YOUR experience what are the main barriers women employees face in the transport sector – such as: - **1. Access to flexible working 2. Culture of the organisation 3. Recruitment policies 4. A lack of visible women role models 5. Managers/Frontline supervisors 6. Lack of suitable PPE and/or uniforms to suit women.** Provide your own barriers in your own words (write down as many as you want) (word cloud feature in Slido)
2. In YOUR experience what are the main facilitators which support women employees in achieving fair employment in the transport sector – such as: **1. Visible women role models 2. Ability for flexible working 3. Male Allies 4. Equal access to education and training 5. Knowledge of the industry and potential employment opportunities 6. Terms and conditions of employment.** Provide your own barriers in your own words (write down as many as you want) (the tool used was SLIDO)

We would appreciate you feedback on our maturity table - self-diagnosis tool

<p>Q1. Please tell us your opinion on the maturity model approach and how effective you believe it can be for an organisation like a transport service provider?</p>	
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<p>Q2. Please tell us your opinion on the contents of the maturity table, do you believe we have included all of the relevant concepts?</p>	
<p>Q3. Do you have any further suggestions to add to the maturity model approach?</p>	

Here below in figure9 an brief overview of the feedback received. The feedback was limited due to the fact that it was asked towards the end of the long session.

Active poll

Q1. Please tell us your opinion on the maturity model approach and how effective you believe it can be for an organisation like a transport service provider? 0 0 3

Really good approach. It is a new approach that would draw attention to specifics, how companies rate themselves with those and what action is required for improvement

I think it could be very useful to use the maturity model approach. It would be very interesting to see the output of such a model.

I think it can be effective to understand the base position and to benchmark.

Join at **slido.com** #19591

Figure 9: Overview of the Feedback collected on the approach during the December 2020 workshop on use case IV and the Dimond Maturity Model approach

4.1.4 Overview of Feedback received

The experts defined fairness in the context of “fair employment for women in the transport sector” to be:

- Equality of pay and working conditions. Equal opportunity for advancement.
- Equal opportunities for access and career
- Equal opportunities
- Flexible working, same training opportunities and promotion for part time staff
- Similar number of male /female managers/supervisors in the workplace
- A level playing field for women to access roles at every level of the business
- It’s about giving equal opportunities irrespective of the background and challenges women have faced to date, it’s fantastic that we are now bringing these to the forefront and there is less stigma associated with what are the challenges females face
- Possibility to reach top positions at the same way than men

- No gender distinction
- Equality of pay and working conditions. Equal opportunity for advancement.

As well as this one expert said:

“By highlighting the range of roles available within the transport industry, encouraging women to apply for opportunities which hold interest for them. Engaging in dialogue with interested individuals to ascertain what their support needs are.

“From my own experience, I accidentally became the youngest Community Rail Partnership Officer in England (possibly the UK) by at least a decade. When I first started the role there were few women in the industry (posts mainly filled by ex-railwaymen of a certain age). Over the last 5 years, I have seen groups such as Women in Community Rail and Women in Rail groups. The groups have worked on combating gender bias, engaging school children, opening up the scope of opportunities beyond the obvious (there is more to the railway industry than drivers, conductors and catering staff)”

In short, inspire, engage, discuss, invite.”

The experts’ opinion on the maturity model approach and how effective they believed it can be for an organisation like a transport service provider were:

- Really good approach. It is a new approach that would draw attention to specifics, how companies rate themselves with those and what action is required for improvement.
- I think it could be very useful to use the maturity model approach. It would be very interesting to see the output of such a model.
- I think it can be effective to understand the base position and to benchmark

In the experts’ opinions the main barriers women employees face in the transport sector are:

- Proper representation in policy shaping positions
- Culture of the industry
- Unconscious bias by men.
- Lack of women role models
- Stereotypes
- Equal fair employment policies
- Equal access to training

- Flexible working

Figure 10: example of feedback received on SLIDO about Fairness definition form the December 2020 workshop

Figure 11: example of screenshot for the world cloud where key facilitators for fairness were discussed

4.2 Use case I, II and III revisions workshop 18th of March

The topics that were discussed at this workshop included:

- a) Exploring the challenges faced and good practices found in transport organisations surrounding appropriate considerations for women as users
- b) The development of a benchmarking or maturity model for fairness in the use of different surface transport services
- c) A workshop discussion to summarise key areas of future work and data collection.

4.2.1 Workshop Agenda

The agenda for the Use Case I, II and III revision workshops in March 2021 is reported in ANNEX II.

4.2.2 Overview of expert invited

Maria Chiara Leva - Lecturer, Technological University Dublin

M. Chiara Leva is a Lecturer in Technological University Dublin in the College of Environmental Health, she is an associated PI in the Science and Technology in Advanced Manufacturing research centre and in the Centre for Innovative Human systems both in Trinity College Dublin. Chiara is the co-chair of technical committee on Human Reliability for the European Safety and Reliability Association, former chair of the Irish Ergonomics Society and co-chair of the scientific steering group for the first Symposium on Human Mental Workload (H-Workload). Dr Leva has more than 70 publications on Human Factors, Operational Risk Assessment and Safety Management in Science and engineering Journals, she is a member of the editorial board for two of those journals.

Yvonne Hail - Research Fellow, University of Stirling

Dr Yvonne Hail is a research fellow at the University of Stirling. Yvonne is a former transport manager who worked in the construction industry in Scotland who is now qualitative researcher with experience in conducting international and interdisciplinary research projects.

Cristina Marolda - Former Policy Officer, Chair of the advisory board for the Diamond project

Cristina Marolda has been for almost 30 years Policy Officer at the European Commission, in charge of Research & Innovation in the transport system. She has always been active in supporting focused research and policy mainstreaming to reach a proper gender balance in mobility. She is now an independent expert on Inclusive Transport Systems and Governance of Innovation and Disruptive Technologies.

Wei-Shiuen Ng - Advisor Sustainable Transport and Global Outreach, International Transport Forum, OECD

Wei-Shiuen Ng is Advisor on Sustainable Transport and Global Outreach in the International Transport Forum (ITF) at the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). She leads gender in transport related research and policy analysis at the ITF, as well as transport and climate change policy development. Wei-Shiuen is also an Adjunct Professor at the Paris Institute of Political Science (Sciences Po), member of the Scientific Committee of the World Conference on Transport Research Society (WCTRS) and co-chairs the Special Interest Group on Transport and Climate Change. She currently serves on the United States Transportation

Research Board (TRB) of the National Academics Committee on Transportation in the Developing Countries and Committee on Transportation Demand management.

4.2.3 Organization and Structure of feedback workshop for Use case I, II and III

The session was attended by 60 participants (externals and project partners). After the explanation of the results from use cases I, II and III, the participants were divided in three discussion groups according to their interest. In each of the groups, use case leaders presented briefly the maturity model and gathered feedback from participants through an interactive tool on the missing aspects and approach.

Use Case I

Feedback session: Surface Transport, fairness and inclusivity

Elements of the maturity model for surface transports that were presented are below:

- Capability to meet user basic transport needs: easy to get to destinations, frequency service, operational hrs, travel information, etc.
- Accessibility: accessibility of the stations and or platform, stops, lighting, cleanliness, seating facilities, parent facilities, comfort, etc.
- Safety and security: safe access and parking, safe belonging and presence of CCTV, possibility of getting help, perception of confidence.

The Maturity questions for self-evaluation were shared. To ask feedback on them the following Pool Questions were used.

1. Please tell us your opinion on the maturity model approach and how effective you believe it can be for an organisation like a transport service provider? **open text box**
2. Please verify how useful and representative you find the following set of questions in relation to self-evaluation of "CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS" in the context of "inclusive transport services:
 - a) Reliability of Service scheduled travel/transit time (how punctual is the service)
 - b) Connectivity and Service coverage (whether or not that are areas isolated due to lack of service)
 - c) Level of service that allows physical access to points of interest
 - d) Facility of intramodality: Integration with other modes of public transport including bus, train, etc
 - e) Operational display of service information/ visible and reliable travel information to destinations
 - f) Available service modes at all operation hours
 - g) Accessible and reliable travel networks to all areas
 - h) Waiting times within travel journey
 - i) Frequency of intermodal connections
 - j) IT systems to provide travel journey real time info and ticketing i.e., travel connections, real times, ticket options and payment plan.

- k) Station integration to multimodal service and multistrip.
 - l) Proximity of alternate modes for last mile connection
 - m) Inclusive/Integrated transit infrastructure design and service e.g., near level platforms/ self-emergency boarding
 - n) Design for Seating and layout
 - o) Real time info/ announcement, wayfinding, and signposting
 - p) Temperature and ventilation control
3. If you think we miss some important questions/ aspects in this section “CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS” on let us know you can mention them here– **such as:** -
4. Please verify how useful and representative you find the following set of questions in relation to self-evaluation of “ACCESSIBILITY” in the context of "inclusive transport services:
- a) Location of Station, Walking time/distance from points of interest to stations and vice versa.
 - b) Barriers that hinder or lessens the choice to walk to and from station to points of interest (for parents)
 - c) Ease of transit between connecting travels (e.g., short distance from one railway line to another)
 - d) Seating to accommodate disabled, carers, women with children etc.
 - e) Good walk pathways (road crossings etc), for managing people flow for all type of users
 - f) Accessibility for Seamless and effectively connection for intramodality with other mode of transport (bus rail metro) for people travelling with dependents
- l) If you think we miss some important questions/ aspects in this section on “ACCESSIBILITY” let us know you can mention them here– **such as:** -
5. Please verify how useful and representative you find the following set of questions in relation to self-evaluation of “SAFETY AND SECURITY” in the context of "inclusive transport service:
- a. Availability of safe complaint information points (i.e to report harassment)
 - b. Availability of platforms and information on personal safety violation
 - c. Well-lit stations with good visibility
 - d. Stations surrounding layout allows for clear visibility of approaching and departing vehicles, amenities, and safety guidelines without discrimination
 - e. Station design allows passengers to be within view of other area, other passengers, staff, and security personnel
 - f. All entrances and exit are within view or clearly signposted with directions of surroundings
 - g. Surveillance and security points clearly visible
 - h. Display advertisements for public awareness campaigns and for publicizing helpline numbers
 - i. Management of room for personal space or crowd control.
 - j. Hardware and software measures for handling overcrowding

- k. Clear Emergency procedures in trains and at stations with detailed evacuation plans
6. If you think we miss some important questions/ aspects in this section on “SAFETY AND SECURITY” let us know you can mention them here– **such as:** -

Use Case II - Feedback session: Autonomous Vehicles, fairness and inclusivity

- Why do we require fairness measures for women in autonomous cars?

In the car industry cars have been designed and developed thinking in technology by itself (technology push development) or when people have been put into the equation, it has been a “medium man”. Thus, there are women needs and requirements that have not been incorporated to the design development.

Elements of the maturity model of Autonomous Cars

- Capacity to meet required needs: ability to travel in an appropriately designed autonomous car, meeting basic expectations and being environmentally sustainable
- Accessible: ability to access activities and services that people have reason to value, accessible to all groups also in terms of design and comfort
- Safe and secure: ability to travel or work safely and securely for all types of users (e.g. income, ethnicity, age, those with children etc.)

To ask feedback on them the following Pool Questions were used.

1. Assess the importance of the following affirmations to increase the acceptability of autonomous car by women related to the capacity to meet the required needs:
 - Autonomous cars will allow to perform simultaneous activities such as interacting with other passengers, especially kids.
 - Autonomous cars will facilitate to perform simultaneously different tasks, including working.
 - Autonomous car will allow me to seize the time, with advanced functionalities for instance when picking the children at school.
 - Autonomous car will reduce the ecological impact and improve the well-being of other road users.

2. Assess the importance of the following affirmations to increase the acceptability of autonomous car by women related to the accessible aspects of the autonomous cars:
 - Autonomous cars will be very flexible in terms of the internal layout allowing different internal configurations to adapt to different needs
 - Autonomous cars will be “children friendly” adapting to the needs of the kids and their caregivers, usually women.

- Autonomous cars will consider the specific ergonomics of women for the interior design and functionality
 - Autonomous cars will promote comfort for all users, considering specific women needs (for instance thermal comfort).
 -
3. Assess the importance of the following affirmations to increase the acceptability of autonomous car by women related to the safety and security aspects of the autonomous cars:
- Autonomous cars will be safe for women (for instance including safety bells for pregnant women)
 - Autonomous cars will allow a level of control and promote a feeling of control according to the different needs of the users.
 - The communication between the car and the user will be adjusted to the context and the preferences of the passengers
 - The autonomous car will communicate with the user using an appropriate language and channel, improving the trust in the system.
 - The users will train with the system allowing different degrees of training according to the preferences of users

Use Case III - Feedback session: Bike sharing, fairness and inclusivity

Elements of the Maturity model for bike sharing:

- Capacity to meet required needs: ability to travel in an appropriately designed transport system, meeting basic expectations, etc.
- Accessibility: to all groups, in terms of design and comfort, fares and costs, etc.
- Safety and Security: travel to work safely and securely for all users

The Maturity questions for self-evaluation were shared. To ask feedback on them the following Pool Questions were used.

- How would YOU define fairness in the context of "Bike-sharing services and women Mobility"
- In YOUR experience or opinion what are the main barriers women face in cycling or using bike-sharing services – **such as:** -
 1. Infrastructure,
 2. Lack of child seats,
 3. Inadequate lighting,
 4. Shortage of bike stations,
 5. No or small carry baskets,
 6. Proximity of stations

Please Provide your own barriers in your own words (write down as many as you want)

- In YOUR experience what are the main opportunities to support women bike-sharing services to provide a better mobility alternative for women (shorter and multi-purpose or multi-stop trips) **Provide your own opportunities, suggestions or recommendations in your own words (write down as many as you want)**
- We would appreciate you feedback on our maturity table - self-diagnosis tool

Q1. Please tell us your opinion on the maturity model approach and how effective you believe it can be for Bike-sharing service operators?	
Q2. Please tell us your opinion on the contents of the maturity table, do you believe we have captured all of the relevant concepts and issues?	
Q3. Do you have any further suggestions to add to the maturity model approach?	

4.2.4 Summary of the Feedback received

Use case I

Capacity to meet required needs:

The statement that was deemed the most useful in relation to self-evaluation of “Capacity to meet required needs” was connectivity and service coverage (whether or not there are areas isolated due to lack of service). The things that were deemed to be more useful included the reliability of service, connectivity and facility of intramodality. While the things that were deemed less useful were available services modes at all operation hours and temperature and ventilation control. Some of the important aspects also considered by the experts were technological apps, accessible ticket options or discounts for travel and travel fares linked to tourist destinations.

How useful and representative you find the following statements in relation to self evaluation of “CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS”

Figure 12 How useful statements in relation to self-evaluation of capacity to meet required needs Use Case I

How useful and representative you find the following statements in relation to self evaluation of "CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS"

Figure 13: How useful statements in relation to self-evaluation of capacity to meet required needs Use Case I

How useful and representative you find the following statements in relation to self evaluation of "CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS"

Figure 14: How useful statements in relation to self-evaluation of capacity to meet required needs Use Case I

Have we missed some important questions/ aspects in this section "CAPACITY TO MEET REQUIRED NEEDS" ? Mentimeter

technological apps, accessible ticket options or discounts for travel, travel fares linked to tourist destinations

travel propose: how the choice of transport is appropriate or not

Ways and means to get information

Ways and means to get information

Accessibility:

The statements in relation to self-evaluation of “Accessibility” were all ranked to be of a similar level of usefulness, including the statements ‘location of station, walking time/distance from points of interest to stations’, ‘Barriers that hinders or lessens the choice to walk to and from station to points of interest (for parents), ‘Ease of transit between connecting travels (e.g. short distance from one railway to another) and ‘Seating to accommodate disabled, carers, women with children etc.’. The statements that were deemed to be the least useful accessibility for an effectively connection for intramodality with other mode of transport for people travelling with dependants’.

How useful and representative you find the following statements in relation to self evaluation of “ACCESSIBILITY”?

Figure 15: How useful statements in relation to self-evaluation of accessibility Use Case 1

How useful and representative you find the following statements in relation to self evaluation of “ACCESSIBILITY”?

Figure 16: How useful statements in relation to self-evaluation of accessibility Use Case 1

Have we missed some important questions/ aspects in this section “ACCESSIBILITY” ?

accessibility of information also for people visually impaired.. or not able to hear

Safety and Security:

The statement that was deemed the most useful in relation to self-evaluation of “Safety and Security” was ‘well-lit stations with good visibility’. ‘Surveillance and security points clearly visible’, exits and entrances are clearly signposted and stations surrounding layout allows for clear visibility of any vehicles, amenities or safety guidelines in the vicinity were also all considered to be important factors in relation to safety and security. While the factors that were deemed to be less useful included ‘display of advertisements for public awareness campaigns and for publicising helpline numbers’ and ‘availability of platforms and information on personal safety violation’.

The experts also gave their opinion on the maturity model approach. While some thought its contents were quite exhaustive others did not think all relevant areas were covered. Some of the comments on the maturity models included that it was dependent upon the level of uptake and benchmarking, on what benefits it can provide for organisations and that it may be useful for progressive updates reviews on needs and enables improvements.

How useful and representative you find the following statements in relation to self evaluation of “SAFETY & SECURITY”?

Figure 17: How useful statements in relation to self-evaluation of safety and security Use Case 1

How useful and representative you find the following statements in relation to self evaluation of "SAFETY & SECURITY"?

Figure 18: How useful statements in relation to self-evaluation of safety and security Use Case 1

How useful and representative you find the following statements in relation to self evaluation of "SAFETY & SECURITY"?

Figure 19: How useful statements in relation to self-evaluation of safety and security Use Case 1

Have we missed some important questions/ aspects in this section "SAFETY & SECURITY" ?

not clear what are the hardware and software measure for overcrowding

Please tell us your opinion on the maturity model approach: how effective you believe it can be?

It depends on the level of uptake and benchmarking..what follow up and benefit are there for company that demonstrate good maturity levels?

quite exhaustive

depending on what benefits it can provide for organisations that assess their maturity level

useful for progressive updates and reviews on needs and enables improvements

Please tell us your opinion on the contents of the maturity table, do you believe we have included all of the relevant concepts?

-

No, but i would need more time to tell what is missing

No, but i need more time to tell you what is missing

Figure 20: Screenshot of other feedback on open ended question collected for Use Case 1

4.2.4.1 [Use case II](#)

Capacity to meet required needs

The affirmations that were deemed the most useful in relation to “Capacity to meet required needs” were that autonomous will reduce the ecological impact and improve the well-being of other road users while the affirmation considered to be the least important was that autonomous cars will allow people to seize the time, with advanced functionalities.

Assess the importance of the following affirmations related to the capacity to meet the required needs

Figure 21: Importance of affirmations related to the capacity to meet required needs with Autonomous cars

In terms of accessibility the most important affirmation considered by the experts was ‘Autonomous cars will consider specific ergonomics of women for the interior design and functionality.’

Assess the importance of the following affirmations related to the accessible aspects of the autonomous cars

Figure 22: Importance of affirmations related to accessibility with Autonomous cars

The most important affirmation considered by the experts for safety and security was that autonomous cars will be safe for women (for instance including safety belts for pregnant women). While the least important affirmation related to safety and security is that the users will train with the system allowing different degrees of training according to the preferences of users

Assess the importance of the following affirmations related to the safety and security aspects of the autonomous cars

Figure 23: Importance of affirmations related to safety and security with Autonomous cars

The experts also gave their opinions on the maturity model approach to this capacity to meet required needs and overall, they commented that it would be most effective if it is based on a self-assessment questionnaire regarding users own level of technological experience.

Please tell us your opinion on the maturity model approach: how effective you believe it can be for an AVs manufacturer?

Please tell us your opinion on the contents of the maturity table, do you believe we have included all of the relevant concepts?

Figure 24: Other feedback collected on Use Case II

4.2.4.2 [Use Case III](#)

Capacity to meet the required needs:

The experts also rated how important capacity to meet required needs is for bike sharing. They rated policy and programme developed to establish stations in low-income and minority neighbourhoods as the most important and policies and programmes to increase the share of electric bikes in the fleet as the least important. When asked if the Diamond team had missed anything and should include something else one expert commented “Perceived risk of vandalism prevents docking stations being put in certain areas causing reduced capacity in these areas. It is important to work with communities to mitigate these concerns”.

Assess the importance of the following affirmations related to the capacity to meet the required needs

Figure 25: Importance of affirmations related to the capacity to meet required needs in bike sharing

Assess the importance of the following affirmations related to the capacity to meet the required needs

Figure 26: Importance of affirmations related to the capacity to meet required needs in bike sharing

Have we missed some important questions/aspects on capacity to meet required needs?

Mentimeter

Figure 27: Other feedback collected on bike sharing needs

Accessibility:

The experts assessed the importance of certain affirmations in relation to accessibility of bike sharing. The affirmation ‘Locating docking stations in low-income communities’ was rated as the most important while ‘policy and schemes developed to ensure stations have shelter’.

Assess the importance of the following affirmations related to accessibility

Figure 28: Importance of affirmations related to accessibility in bike sharing

Assess the importance of the following affirmations related to accessibility

Figure 29: Importance of affirmations related to accessibility in bike sharing

Have we missed some important questions/aspects on accessibility?

Structures large enough to welcome cargo bikes

Figure 30: Other feedback collected on Accessibility of bike sharing

Safety and Security

The experts also rated how important aspects of safety and security were. Programmes to ensure bikes are functional and well maintained (e.g., well-functioning lights and brakes etc) were rated the most important while programme developed to provide safety equipment at the stations such as helmets, high-vis vests and rain ponchos for users was rated of the lowest importance.

The experts also gave their opinion on the maturity model approach. The consensus was that it is a good model.

Assess the importance of the following affirmations related to safety and security

Figure 31: Importance of affirmations related to safety and security in bike sharing

Assess the importance of the following affirmations related to safety and security

Figure 32: Importance of affirmations related to safety and security in bike sharing

Please tell us your opinion on the maturity model approach: how effective you believe it can be?

I think it a very good one.

Effective

I think it looks like a good model, but without having a fuller understanding of this and alternative models I'm not sure I am qualified to comment!

Figure 33: Other feedback collected for maturity model approach in bike sharing

5 Development of online Bayesian Belief Networks for the use cases to allow simulation of fairness parameters and their impact on user satisfaction.

The data and results obtained from the UESI and from the observations were used to set up an online version of the Bayesian networks using the Hugin Platform to allow users to connect online and access the model to verify how each fairness characteristics in each use case impacted the likelihood of fuser satisfaction for different categories of users (considering demographic characteristics on each use case).

5.1 Use Case 1 model.

The input data for the model was obtained from questionnaires applied on a wide range of population from Poland and Spain. The questionnaires covered indicators on station properties (e.g., platform and concourse), social and demographic information. The complete data was split into training and test sets (in a ratio of 3:1). The training data was used to define the parameters of the Bayesian Network model by implementing learning algorithms. Once the model was completely defined, the test data set was used to assess the performance of the model. The target variable was defined as Travel Satisfaction. This variable provides information on the contentment level of users using the travel network in different countries. One of the challenges of this study was the limited size of dataset. In response to this, fixed structure models such as the Naïve Bayes Model were defined. This model consists in a finite number of feature variables that depend on a single node known as the class variable (Jensen et al 2007). In addition, reduced state space using expert knowledge, hierarchical model to reflect groups of nodes were determined.

The steps in the model development are the following:

1. Factor analysis on indicators from questionnaire. Produced factors 0 – 3 – named using expert knowledge.
2. Feature selection on station, social and demographic indicators using an inclusive wrapper approach (F1-score used) assuming a naïve Bayes model structure and training data to score.
 - a. Certain indicators of special interest for the analysis and use of the model were included in the model despite being removed by the feature selection (e.g., sex)
3. Introduced layer of hidden nodes between target and each group of factors (seven groups)
 - a. Considered the hidden nodes for each factor group independently (due to complete data)
 - b. Used the Expectation-Maximization algorithm with AIC as model score to identify the number of states of the hidden node. The search started from 2 states up to 10 states (if 10 states produced the highest score, the limit was increase to 15).
 - c. The model producing the highest AIC score was selected
4. The final model structure was created by combining the models for each factor group into a single structure

Figure 34: Structure of Bayesian Network Model for predicting travel satisfaction based on fairness characteristics and structural data.

The Value of information on each factor captures the value of being able to know each factor condition even before making a travel satisfaction prediction. The results show the value of information of each of the selected factor variables relative to the Travel Satisfaction before the decision. There is one bar for each information variable labelled with their corresponding name. The size of the bar is proportional to a factor of the maximum expected utility of the decision.

Figure 35: Value of information of hidden nodes representing each factor.

The performance of the final model was assessed on the test dataset using Area Under the Curve. The model performance was compared with the performance of the naïve Bayes model. Other model structures were considered but found to produce a lower AUC score.

The Model performance, in terms of Area under the Curve is reported in the Figure below.

Figure 36: Model performance for Use case I.

The BBN model for predicting travel satisfaction has been implemented in an online platform open to the public²². The platform allows visualising the graph of the network as a way to represent the dependencies of the variables involved in the model. Also, a number of “what-if” scenarios can be defined to assess the impact of factors such as demographics, station status or questionnaire, in the Travel satisfaction. This can be done by selecting the parameters for each factor through the interactive menus.

²² <http://demo.hugin.com/example/TravelSatisfaction>

By: Chiara, Luca, Alberto, Anders, Nicolaj
 WWW: Anders L Madsen

Created: 2021-02-01
 Latest update: 2021-03-26

Travel Satisfaction Prediction

Some introduction

Below is a set of HUGIN widgets for interacting with the model:

Travel Satisfaction

Reset Value of Information Explanation

Demographics Station Questionnaire

Demographics Characteristics

Age

Ethnicity

Sex

Status

Discrimination

Sexual orientation

Travelling with dep

Environment

Travel to work method

Caring responsibility

Figure 37. Website preview of travel satisfaction prediction tool.

5.2 Use Case II model.

This model focuses on the autonomous vehicles Acceptance among general population. The input data was collected through a series of questionnaires applied on a diverse range of population going from people with different ages to different vehicle needs. One of the challenges encountered during this study is related to the missing factor analysis. For this reason, a simple Naïve Bayes Model with no hidden nodes was defined. This approach allowed to also overcome the problem related to the limited size of dataset. The defined model was defined including only variables with value of information higher that 0.005.

Figure 38: Overview of the Naive Bayes network built for Use case II limited UESI data set

In this model the Value of information for each factor captures the value of being able to know each element condition before making a prediction on the Acceptance variable.

Figure 39: Value of information for Autonomous vehicle acceptance model.

A webpage²³ has been developed to give access to the autonomous vehicle acceptance model. Visualisation of the relevant variables for the analysis are displayed in the model graph. In addition, a number of scenario combinations can be defined in the interactive menus.

HUGIN Demo Demos (finance) ▾ Demos (ecosystem services) ▾ Demos (misc) ▾ Demos (projects) ▾ About

By: Chiara, Diego, Anders
 WWW: Anders L Madsen
 Created: 2021-05-28
 Latest update: 2021-05-28

Autonomous Vehicle Acceptance Prediction

Some introduction

Below is a set of HUGIN widgets for interacting with the model:

Autonomous Vehicle Acceptance

ACCEPTANCE
 7.95%
 42.00%

Reset Value of Information Explanation

Demographics Station Questionnaire

Company KPI Inclusiveness Monitor

BENEFITS_ECO
 6.82%
 69.18%

TRUST
 11.36%
 88.64%

Travel_time
 1.80%
 2.90%
 1.85%
 4.99%
 9.17%
 1.85%
 1.85%
 17.54%
 10.31%
 2.90%
 20.77%
 1.80%
 2.42%
 6.04%
 8.13%
 5.56%

EXCITEMENT_DRIVE_AV
 23.89%
 78.14%

Figure 40. Use Case II website screenshot.

5.3 Use Case III model.

This network represents the likelihood of users being satisfied with the how the bike sharing services fulfil their travel needs.

²³ <http://demo.hugin.com/example/AutonomousVehicleAcceptance>

Figure 43: Model performance use case III

A webpage²⁴ has been developed to give access to the Bike Sharing Service Satisfaction model. Visualisation of the relevant variables for the analysis are displayed in the model graph. In addition, a number of scenario combinations can be defined in the interactive menus.

²⁴ <http://demo.hugin.com/example/BikeSharingServiceSatisfaction>

By: Chiara, Diego, Anders
 WWW: Anders L Madsen
 Created: 2021-05-11
 Latest update: 2021-05-19

Bike Sharing Service Satisfaction Prediction

Some introduction

Below is a set of HUGIN widgets for interacting with the model:

Bike Sharing Satisfaction

Reset Value of Information Explanation

Demographics Station Questionnaire

Figure 44. Website preview containing Use Case III model.

5.4 Use Case IV model.

This network represents the likelihood of users being satisfied with inclusiveness

Figure 45: Bayesian network on organisation inclusive satisfaction.

Following the design thinking sessions, the work for task 5.1 has continued with an analysis of the outcomes of these sessions, to refine customer journey mapping, understand what

Figure 46: Value of information of organisation inclusive satisfaction model.

The Model performance, in terms of Area under the Curve is reported in the Figure below.

Figure 47: Model performance use case IV.

An online version of the predictive model for organizational inclusive satisfaction can be found on the website²⁵. A capture of the website is showed below.

²⁵ <http://demo.hugin.com/example/OrgInclusiveSatisfaction>

By: Chiara, Diego, Anders
 WWW: Anders L Madsen
 Created: 2021-05-21
 Latest update: 2021-05-21

Organizational Inclusive Satisfaction Prediction

Some introduction

Below is a set of HUGIN widgets for interacting with the model:

Organizational Inclusive Satisfaction

Reset Value of Information Explanation

Demographics Station Questionnaire

Figure 48: Website preview for Use Case IV model.

6 Conclusions

This deliverable presented an overview of the activities of WP 4 of the DIAMOND project leading us to the definition of a Diamond Fairness Maturity Model that is now informing the toolbox architecture.

Thanks to these activities, the work for the development of each of the tools composing the toolbox has started. Concretely, the self-diagnosis tool is being developed in task 5.2, the decision-support system in task 5.3, and the development of simulation system for impact assessment in task 5.4.

For this reason, this architecture will serve as a foundation of a Web-based toolbox, which will be available online at the end of the project for other organisation to use as a benchmark of the level of fairness and inclusivity they offer in their mobility services or as part of their employment conditions.

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ANNEX I: Agenda DIAMOND workshop 14th of December 2020: Women employed in Transport: challenges and good practices

WEBINAR

WOMEN EMPLOYED IN TRANSPORT

Challenges and good practice from a surface transport perspective

14th December 2020
14:00 – 16:00h UK time

The DIAMOND Project invites you to take part in an interactive webinar conference to discuss the barriers and facilitators faced by women as employees across the transport sector.

The format will be a panel discussion between our academic researchers and you, the professionals from the transport sector, in order to ensure relevant findings are translated accurately into outputs suitable for transport organisations.

We would very much like you to be part of the overall discussion.

Topics for discussion:

1. Exploring the challenges faced and good practices found in transport organisations surrounding women as employees
2. The development of a benchmarking or maturity model for fairness in women's employment in the transport sector
3. A workshop discussion to summarise key areas of future work and data collection

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Transport plays an important role in our economies and societies and has a large impact on growth and employment. A recent EU report claimed that the transport industry directly employs around 10 million people and accounts for about 5% of gross domestic product (GDP). Currently Women account for only 22% of the work force in the transport sector affecting employment equality and diversity in perspectives.

To create a fair and inclusive society where equality of outcome is important and where no-one is disadvantaged relative to another by virtue of their gender, the European Union (EU) commissioned project DIAMOND to collect and analyse gender disaggregated data to develop a toolbox for transport equity analysis to enhance fair employment for women in the transport sector.

To this end we have been collecting primary data from across Europe, the UK and Ireland to identify the barriers and facilitators of women employees across the sector in order to develop guidelines for transport operators to help them improve the fair and inclusive recruitment, retention, and promotion of women in the sector.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 824326.

AGENDA

14.00 – Welcome and introduction

Yvonne Hail, Research Fellow, Management School of the University of Stirling
Cristina Marolda, Former Policy Officer (DG MOVE), European Commission

14.10 – The gender dimension of the transport workforce

Wei-Shiuen Ng, Advisor of sustainable transport and global outreach, International Transport Forum, OECD

14.17 – Employment opportunities in Smart Mobility

Isolda Constantin, TinnGO project partner, TinnGO
Stefan Roseanu, TinnGO project partner, Integral Consulting R&D

14.25 – Working with our members to identify and address the challenges faced by women in the Rail Sector

Lorna Gibson, Training Director, QTS Group, founder member of Women in Rail

14.35 – Q&A

14.40 – Opportunities and challenges of women employed in transport

Linda Allan, Talent Manager, Irish Rail

14.50 – Senior women in Rail

Charlene Wallace, Director Networkrail, Women in Rail

15.00 – Q&A

WOMEN EMPLOYED IN TRANSPORT
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AGENDA

15.10 – Experiences from the front line

Heather Waugh, *Train Driver, Women in Rail*

15.20 – Yes! More Women in Transport – Making Transport Fit for Women to Work in

Inga-Lena Heinsch, *Political Assistant, European Transport Workers' Federation (ETF)*

15.30 – Q&A

15.35 – DIAMOND initial findings and workshop

Yvonne Hail, *Research Fellow, Management School of the University of Stirling*

Chiara Lava, *Lecturer, TU Dublin*

The workshop will provide us with an opportunity to discuss how best to take these research findings and employee experiences forwards to ensure that all women employed across the transports sector, no matter their age, ability/disability or caring responsibilities have access to safe, fair and inclusive employment.

15.55 – Closure of the webinar

Yvonne Hail, *Research Fellow, Management School of the University of Stirling*

Cristina Marolda, *Former Policy Officer (DG MOVE), European Commission*

WOMEN EMPLOYED IN TRANSPORT
Challenges and good practice from a surface transport perspective

SPEAKERS

In order of appearance

Cristina Marolda

Former Policy Officer, European Commission

Cristina Marolda has been for almost 30 years Policy Officer at the European Commission, in charge of Research & Innovation in the transport system. She has always been active in supporting focused research and policy mainstreaming to reach a proper gender balance in mobility.

She is now an Independent expert on Inclusive Transport Systems and Governance of Innovation and Disruptive Technologies.

Yvonne Hail

Research fellow, University of Stirling

Dr Yvonne Hail is a research fellow at the university of Stirling. Yvonne is a former transport manager who worked in the construction industry in Scotland who is now qualitative researcher with experience in conducting international and interdisciplinary research projects.

Wei-Shiuen Ng

Advisor Sustainable Transport and Global Outreach, International Transport Forum, OECD

Wei-Shiuen Ng is the author of the ITF Report "The Gender Dimension of the Transport Workforce". Wei-Shiuen is a member of the Scientific Committee of the World Conference on Transport Research Society (WCTRS) and co-chairs the Special Interest Group on Transport and Climate Change. She is a Research Affiliate at Stanford University, an Honorary Research Associate at the University of Oxford and a guest editor of "Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment".

WOMEN EMPLOYED IN TRANSPORT
Challenges and good practice from a surface transport perspective

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WOMEN EMPLOYED IN TRANSPORT
Challenges and good practice from a surface transport perspective

Lorna Gibson
Training Director, QTS Group

Lorna Gibson is Training Director for the QTS Group, a large enterprise owned by Renew Holdings and supplying Railway Infrastructure Engineering services throughout the United Kingdom. Lorna's key role within the Group is that of Managing Director of QTS Training Ltd, a subsidiary company which supplies railway safety, on-track plant, health and safety and construction management training to the rail and wider industries.

Lorna is also a Director, and Past President, of the Ayrshire Chamber of Commerce and Industry, sits on the Developing Young Workforce Ayrshire Steering Group, is a founding member of Women in Rail Scotland, sits on the NSAR Rail Apprenticeship Quality Board and is Vice Chair of the Hansal Foundation.

Linda Allen
Talent Manager, Irish Rail

Experienced Talent Manager with a demonstrated history of working in the transportation/trucking/railroad industry. Skilled in coaching, Training Programme Design, Training Delivery, Management, leadership, Interviewing, and Personality Testing. Strong human resources professional with a Master's degree focused in Work and Organisational Psychology from Dublin City University.

Charlene Wallace
Director Networkrail, Women in Rail

Charlene brings over 20 years' experience in the public transport sector having previously held senior board director roles in rail and aviation, including most recently with Virgin Trains. She has a strong track record of delivering and leading customer-focused transformation in transport and has a wide range of transition and business change experience including - improving customer and stakeholder processes and communications, delivering customer initiatives, employee engagement and organisational change.

Charlene's focus at Network Rail will be with our customers and passengers. She will be leading the National Passenger and Customer Experience team (NP&Cx), which includes the national stations team, and the new Passenger Information During Disruption (PIDD) team. She is also the Interim Director for Freight, representing the interests of the rail freight industry across the UK.

WOMEN EMPLOYED IN TRANSPORT
Challenges and good practice from a surface transport perspective

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WOMEN EMPLOYED IN TRANSPORT
Challenges and good practice from a surface transport perspective

Heather Waugh
Train Driver, Women in Rail

Heather Waugh joined the railway as a Train Driver with Scotrail in August 2006, having previously been an Operational Manager with Royal Mail for 10 years. In January 2019 Heather became Freightliner's first ever female train driver in Scotland and, indeed, the only female freight train driver at all in Scotland.

She is passionate about issues around mental health, equality, diversity and inclusion and believes strongly in breaking down barriers, both mental and physical, which prevent women from excelling in areas that are still heavily male dominated within the rail industry. She won 'Highly Commended' at the Women in Rail Awards 2020 in the category of 'Inspirational Woman of the Year'.

Maria Chiara Leva
Lecturer, Technological University Dublin

Maria Chiara Leva is a Lecturer in Technological University Dublin in the College of Environmental Health, she is an associated PI in the Science and Technology in Advanced Manufacturing research centre and in the Centre for Innovative Human systems both in Trinity College Dublin. Chiara is the co-chair of the technical committee on Human Reliability for the European Safety and Reliability Association, former chair of the Irish Ergonomics Society and co-chair of the scientific steering group for the first Symposium on Human Mental Workload (H-Workload). Dr Leva has more than 70 publications on Human Factors, Operational Risk Assessment and Safety Management in Science and Engineering Journals, she is a member of the editorial board for two of those journals.

WOMEN EMPLOYED IN TRANSPORT
Challenges and good practice from a surface
transport perspective

MORE INFORMATION

<https://diamond-project.eu/webinar-women-employed-in-transport/>

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 824326.

ANNEX II: Agenda DIAMOND Workshop 18th of March 2021: Fairness for Women as users of Surface Transport Services: challenges and good Practices

WEBINAR

FAIRNESS FOR WOMEN AS USERS OF SURFACE TRANSPORT SERVICES

Challenges and good practice

18th March 2021
14:00 – 16:30h GMT time (15.00-17.30 CET)

The **DIAMOND Project** invites you to take part in an interactive webinar conference to discuss the barriers and facilitators faced by women as users of surface transport services.

The format will be a panel discussion between our academic researchers and you, the professionals from the transport sector and transport experts, in order to ensure relevant findings are translated accurately into outputs suitable for transport organisations.

We would very much like you to be part of the overall discussion.

Topics for discussion:

1. Exploring the challenges faced and good practices found in transport organisations surrounding appropriate considerations for women as users.
2. The development of a benchmarking or maturity model for fairness in the use of different surface transport services
3. A workshop discussion to summarise key areas of future work and data collection

JOIN HERE!

Transport plays an important role in our economies and societies and has a large impact on growth and employment. To create a fair and inclusive society where equality of outcome is important and where no-one is disadvantaged relative to another by virtue of their gender, the European Union (EU) commissioned project DIAMOND to collect and analyse gender disaggregated data to develop a toolbox for transport equity analysis to enhance fair access for women as users of transport services.

To this end we have been collecting primary data from across Europe, the UK and Ireland to identify the barriers and facilitators of primarily women as users of transport services across Europe in order to develop guidelines for transport operators to help them improve a fair and inclusive service provision.

AGENDA

14.00 – Welcome and introduction

M. Chiara Leva, Yvonne Hail, *DIAMOND project*

Maria Cristina Marolda, *Former European Commission Policy Officer, Transport Expert*

SECTION I: Surface transport fairness & inclusivity

14.10 – The gender dimension of travel behaviour

Wei-Shiuen Ng, *Advisor of sustainable transport and global outreach, International Transport Forum, OECD*

14.20 – Issues raised and challenges faced by women in surface transport

Chiara Leva, *Lecturer, TU Dublin*

Mary Kinahan, Ajeni Thimnu, Akansha Lohmore, *Researchers, TU Dublin*

14.35 - Q&A and poll

SECTION II: Bicycle sharing: fairness & inclusivity

14.45 – Opportunities and challenges for women using bike sharing services: **DIAMOND data collection results**

Janet Horner, *Green Party Councillor, Dublin North Inner City Representative*

14.55 – Opportunities and challenges for women using bike sharing services: **DIAMOND data collection results**

Wafza Saleh, *Professor, Augustus Ababio-Donkor, Researcher, Edinburg Napier University*

Chris Blache, *Urban Anthropologist, co-founder, Genre & Ville*

15.10 – Q&A and poll

SECTION III: Autonomous Vehicles: fairness & inclusivity

15:20 - Women experience and preferences as AV users

Begoña Matea, and Ricard Barberà, *Human Factor Researchers, IBV*

15.35 – Q&A and poll

Discussion session with attendees

15:45 – 16:25 – **Parallel feedback sessions on fairness & inclusivity for the public transport sector, bicycle sharing and autonomous vehicles.**

FAIRNESS FOR WOMEN AS USERS OF SURFACE TRANSPORT SERVICES
Challenges and good practice

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 824326.

SPEAKERS

In order of appearance

Maria Cristina Marolda

Former European Commission Policy Officer, Transport Expert

Cristina Marolda has been for almost 30 years Policy Officer at the European Commission, in charge of Research & Innovation in the transport system. She has always been active in supporting focused research and policy mainstreaming to reach a proper gender balance in mobility.

She is now an independent expert on Inclusive Transport Systems and Governance of Innovation and Disruptive Technologies.

Yvonne Hail

Research fellow, University of Stirling

Dr Yvonne Hail is a research fellow at the university of Stirling. Yvonne is a former transport manager who worked in the construction industry in Scotland who is now qualitative researcher with experience in conducting international and interdisciplinary research projects.

Wei-Shiuen Ng

Advisor Sustainable Transport and Global Outreach, International Transport Forum, OECD

Wei-Shiuen Ng is Advisor on Sustainable Transport and Global Outreach in the International Transport Forum (ITF) at the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). She leads gender in transport related research and policy analysis at the ITF, as well as transport and climate change policy development. Wei-Shiuen is also an Adjunct Professor at the Paris Institute of Political Science (Sciences Po), a member of the Scientific Committee of the World Conference on Transport Research Society (WCTRS) and co-chairs the Special Interest Group on Transport and Climate Change. She currently serves on the United States Transportation Research Board (TRB) of the National Academies Committee on Transportation in the Developing Countries and Committee on Transportation Demand Management.

**FAIRNESS FOR WOMEN AS USERS OF
SURFACE TRANSPORT SERVICES**

Maria Chiara Leva
Lecturer, Technological University Dublin

Maria Chiara Leva is a Lecturer in Technological University Dublin in the College of Environmental Health, she is an associated PI in the Science and Technology in Advanced Manufacturing research centre and in the Centre for Innovative Human systems both in Trinity College Dublin. Chiara is the co-chair of the technical committee on Human Reliability for the European Safety and Reliability Association, former chair of the Irish Ergonomics Society and co-chair of the scientific steering group for the first Symposium on Human Mental Workload (H-Workload). Dr Leva has more than 70 publications on Human Factors, Operational Risk Assessment and Safety Management in Science and Engineering Journals, she is a member of the editorial board for two of those journals.

Ajeni Ari Thimnu
Researcher, Technological University Dublin

A researcher at Technological University Dublin focused on the area of Gender and Transport in the school of Environmental Health. She is a graduate of Supply Chain Management of the National Institute for Transport and Logistics, TU Dublin and hold a degree in Business Management.

Mary Kinahan
Researcher, Technological University Dublin

Dr. Mary Kinahan is an organisational psychologist and lecturer in Organisational Behaviour and Human Resource Management at TU Dublin. Mary is a SAT member for the Athena Swan Bronze Award committee in Dublin Institute of Technology and is currently involved in various gender focused projects, such as DIAMOND (H2020), and in supervising PhD candidates in gender focused areas. Mary completed her PhD in Organisational and Social Psychology at DCU Business School in November 2013. Her paper entitled "Hierarchy Enhancing vs. Hierarchy Attenuating: Do men and women differ in their preferences for leadership roles" was a finalist for best paper at the 16th Congress of EAWOP in Munster, Germany. Mary was supervised by Dr. Janine Bosak and collaborated with Professor Alice H. Eagly of Northwestern University, USA.

**FAIRNESS FOR WOMEN AS USERS OF
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FAIRNESS FOR WOMEN AS USERS OF SURFACE TRANSPORT SERVICES

Janet Horner

Green Party Councillor, Dublin North Inner City Representative

Janet Horner is a Green Party Councillor for Dublin's North Inner City. She chairs the walking and cycling sub-committee on Dublin City Council. She is a long-time cycling campaigner through Dublin Cycling Campaign and with Monthly Cycles - a sociable and inclusive cycling initiative for women and others of all abilities.

Wafaa Saleh

Professor, Edinburgh Napier University

Wafaa Saleh is a Chartered Engineer with over 30 years' experience in teaching, research and practice. The main focus of her research interests includes modelling travel behaviour, transport demand management, accident analysis and investigations and transport and the environment. Wafaa has successfully published over 100 articles and edited few books and Special Issues at top academic international transport Journals. She has been invited as keynote addresses and to international external examinations. Wafaa has a vision for her research and academic activities "Our academic research and scholar activities have to have a positive contribution to the development and wellbeing of our communities". Impacts of transport and travel on the community have been the highlight of a number of her teaching and research activities. She is marketing this vision in international talks, publications and other scholarly activities.

Augustus Ababio-Donkor

Research Assistant, Transport Research Institute, Edinburgh Napier University

Dr Augustus Ababio-Donkor is a Research Assistant at the Transport Research Institute, Edinburgh Napier University. Prior to his PhD studies, Augustus was a Senior Engineer at the Department of Urban Roads (DUR), Ghana (2007-2016). Augustus had his Masters and PhD degrees in Transport Planning and Engineering. His research interests include travel demand modelling, behavioural economics and behavioural based travel modelling.

FAIRNESS FOR WOMEN AS USERS OF SURFACE TRANSPORT SERVICES
Challenges and good practice

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Train Driver, Women in Rail

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WOMEN EMPLOYED IN TRANSPORT
Challenges and good practice from a surface transport perspective

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WOMEN EMPLOYED IN TRANSPORT
 Challenges and good practice from a surface
 transport perspective

MORE INFORMATION

<https://diamond-project.eu/diamond-webinar-women-surface-transport-users/>

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